

Predictive toxicology using QSAR : A perspective[†]

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Abstract : The need of *in silico* techniques in predicting toxicological and hazardous properties of chemicals are taking the central stage of attention day by day among the scientific community and the public. *In silico* methods are capable of providing information about the physicochemical properties of chemicals, their environmental fate as well as their human health effects. Quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) is one of the mostly used techniques among different *in silico* approaches. QSAR will complement the "3Rs" (replacement, refinement and reduction of animals in research) with a powerful new tool to minimize animal testing. Advanced QSAR predictive models are being designed and tested by different countries governing regulatory agencies to assess physical, chemical, and biological properties of individual chemical entities using applications specific for decision-making frameworks in safety assessments. The use of QSAR modelling for toxicological predictions would help to determine the potential adverse effects of chemical entities in risk assessment, chemical screening, and priority setting. Again, in pre-screening of new drug entities before preclinical trial, QSAR can be proved as a significant tool for predicting preclinical toxicological endpoints and clinical adverse effects. A major objective of employing these software programs is to facilitate industry scientists not only to improve the discovery process but also to ensure the sensible use of *in silico* tools to support risk assessments of chemicals and drug-induced toxicities and in safety evaluations. Though few expert systems are available, yet a large number of expert systems should be developed for the ease of toxicity screenings of chemicals and pharmaceuticals in less time employing less money and avoiding the sacrifice of large number of animals. In this review, representative examples of different recently reported QSAR models, expert systems and available databases and the current capabilities and limitations of *in silico* approaches are critically addressed.

Keywords : QSAR, toxicity, chemical, REACH, pharmaceutical, ecotoxicity, adverse drug reaction.

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1. Introduction

Toxicity, deals with the adverse or annoying effects of chemicals on ecosystem, humans or other living systems in the environment¹. Majority of chemicals are potential poisons since they can cause injury or death due to their excessive exposure at various concentrations. The ultimate adverse effect of a toxic chemical is death but less severe adverse effects may also be increased day by day. The problems are following : (1) food consumption altered, (2) body and organ weights changed, (3) visible pathological changes and (4) altered enzyme levels or altered biochemical processes¹.

The increasing environmental pollution and the continuous development of new chemicals have led to an ever growing concern about the potential effects that they

may have on human health directly or indirectly and the environment also. The consequence of perilous chemicals, pharmaceuticals, food products, pesticides, dyes and pollutants on the ecosystem is a matter of great apprehension considering that though huge numbers of compounds are in commercial use, relatively few of these have been subjected to sufficient evaluation for their hazardous environmental properties².

The large-scale production of chemicals has increased from merely 1 million tons to 400 million tons in the last six decades. Around 100000 different chemicals are registered in the European market of which 10% are marketed in volumes of more than 10 tons, and a further 20% are marketed at 1–10 tons every year³. Testing and assessment of their risks to human health and the envi-

ronment according to the European Commission Directive 67/548 are required before marketing in volumes above 10 kg/year. In case of larger volumes, more in-depth testing and focusing on long-term and chronic effects are essential⁴. In contrast, more than 99% of the total volumes of all substances in the market are not subjected to the same testing requirements. Most of them have never been tested at all³. The experimental determination of environmental parameters (e.g. soil sorption, bioconcentration, biodegradation and biotransformation, toxic effects) of commercial chemicals is a costly and time consuming process. Since there is large number of chemicals currently in common use and new chemicals are registered at a very high rate, it is obvious that our human and material resources are insufficient to obtain experimentally even basic information on environmental fate and effects for all these chemicals. Thus, it is necessary to develop quantitative models that will accurately and readily predict environmental behaviour of large sets of chemicals. A chemistry approach to predictive toxicology relies on quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) modelling to predict biological activity from chemical structure. Such approaches have proven capabilities when applied to well-defined toxicity end points or regions of chemical space. Like environmental toxicity, prediction of toxicity or side effects of pharmaceuticals is an important step during initial phases of drug development to avoid larger losses at later stages. Though experimental toxicity testing using animal models is unavoidable for drug candidates at an advanced stage of drug development research, *in silico* prediction of toxicity of drug compounds provides a tool for initial screening of candidate molecules for probable synthesis and development.

Acceptable ADME-Tox (Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Excretion and Toxicity) properties are mandatory for the successful development of a new drug entity⁵. Adverse Drug Reactions (ADRs) represent a major worry for the pharmaceutical industry because of drug withdrawal at the final stage of drug development. It represents a significant loss of investment in human efforts and technical resources⁶. A rational approach should be adopted in the earlier stages of the drug development process to amplify the effectiveness and diminish the cost of pharmaceutical R&D as well as to reduce the failure

rate of new drug development in the earlier stages of the process. This strategy has been widely acknowledged by the pharmaceutical industries⁷. The major approach towards this involves *in silico* ADME-Tox evaluations into early drug discovery stages which may result in cost and time savings⁷.

Drug-induced toxicity problem is notable, and the toxic effects from marketed drugs, even when used appropriately, are estimated to rank among the top 10 causes of death in the United States⁸. Drug induced toxicity is one of the most major causes of 1/5th of the dropouts during late drug development stages. Nearly 25% of all marketed drugs have at least one positive genotoxicity test result⁹. As a result, implementing toxicity testing as early as possible in the drug development process has a significant value⁶.

Pharmaceutical companies conduct earlier screening for drug induced toxicity due to following reasons : (i) large amounts of compounds required for the *in vivo* studies, (ii) lack of reliable high-throughput *in vitro* assays and (iii) inability of *in vitro* and animal models to predict correctly some human toxicities. To eradicate the inconvenience, computational (*in silico*) toxicity prediction tools serve as one of the main approaches to find out the potential toxic effects of drugs on humans even before having the compounds in market physically¹⁰.

In this background, the alarming situation of eco-toxicity, aquatic toxicity of diverse chemicals, environmental fate parameters, health effects of organic chemicals and drug induced toxicity have compelled different government and non-government chemical regulatory authorities to recommend the application of theoretical, non-experimental, non-animal, alternative, and in particular, *in silico*, methods to provide information about the basic physicochemical and fate properties of chemicals as well as their ecological and human health effects before they reach into market for public use. Computer-aided toxicity prediction with sophisticated software packages makes use of the relationship between chemical structure and biological activity (toxicity) to compute such properties. In this scenario, use of quantitative structure-toxicity relationship (QSTR) as one of the non-experimental methods is important in order to reduce time and cost involvement in design, development and discovery process of chemicals and drugs.

2. Predictive toxicology using *in silico* tools

2.1. Motivation and strengths of predicting toxicity (*in silico*) of chemicals and pharmaceuticals

Motivation behind the predicting the toxicity and fate of chemicals varies from user to user. Here, we describe some of the key reasons for which models have been developed.

(1) Pressure to reduce animal testing

From last two decades there has been growing public concern regarding the use of animals in testing, especially in toxicology and medical research. The major concern over animal welfare has been intense in Europe and in the UK in particular. Campaigners for animal welfare cite a number of approaches to reduce and ultimately replace animal tests. These include the use of validated alternative tests such as *in vitro* and cell culture techniques, as well as the computer-aided prediction of toxicity. The status of alternative techniques is well reviewed by Worth and Balls¹¹. There is clearly a role for predictive techniques in the replacement of animal tests, either as stand-alone methods, or more commonly as part of a tiered assessment strategy.

(2) Computational models provide suitable toxicity prediction

Computer models allow for the effects of chemicals (physicochemical properties, toxicological activity, distribution, fate, etc.) to be easily predicted. These predictions may be obtained from knowledge of chemical structure alone. For most methods, provided that the chemical structure can be described in two (or occasionally three) dimensions, the effects may be predicted. Information regarding the chemicals may be gained without chemical testing, or even the need to synthesize the chemical.

(3) Legislation

Governmental policies in both the European Union (EU) and North America have encouraged and, in some cases, mandated the use of computational techniques to predict toxicity. For example, the US EPA has utilized QSAR to assist in the pre-manufacture notification of new chemicals, especially where no toxicity data physically in hand. This requirement for models has inspired considerable advancement in the prediction of acute toxicity for environmental endpoints.

(4) Filling data gaps

Around 100000 separate chemicals may be released into the environment annually; it is alarming to consider that dependable toxicity data exist for only a small proportion of these chemicals, probably less than 5%. The percentage of chemicals with a complete set of reliable toxicity data (i.e. across a broad spectrum of environmental and human health effects) is considerably less than 5%. Computer-aided prediction of toxicity has the capability to assist in the prioritisation of chemicals for testing, and for predicting specific toxicities to allow for labelling. Due to the reliability of models for toxicity prediction, there will undoubtedly be an increased use of QSARs for the filling of data gaps.

(5) Cost and time reduction

Toxicological testing is very costly in terms of the animals used and time taken. Even a simple ecotoxicological assay may cost several thousand dollars, and a two-year carcinogenicity assay may cost several million dollars. Cost is a clear issue to fill the data gaps for the many new compounds that have not been tested. On the other hand, prediction of various toxicity endpoints for drug candidates at an early stage of design can save large amount of expenses for such compounds which may be found toxic at a later stage of drug development programme.

(6) Identification of new toxicological problems

The development of computational techniques not only allows for the prediction of the potential for estrogenicity to be made, but also allows for rational direction to be given to testing programs. The modelling of estrogenicity is an excellent example of the application of tools developed primarily for drug design (i.e. 3D QSAR and Comparative Molecular Field Analysis [CoMFA]) to toxicological prediction. The phenomenon of endocrine disruption came to the forefront during the 1990s.

(7) Designing of new compounds

To increase the efficacy of drugs and agrochemicals, computer-aided activity is largely used in recent time. Computer-aided modelling may be used to identify the possible toxic effects induced from pharmaceuticals or those associated with unwanted ADME profile at the early stage of drug discovery.

(8) Higher throughput and *in silico* approaches have higher reproducibility if the same model is used. Again, this *in silico* approaches have low compound synthesis requirement.

(9) *In silico* models have the ability to predict ADME-related properties on virtual structures enabling exploration of chemical space without the need to create wet chemical laboratory synthesis and experimental testing until a likely hit or candidate molecule is selected.

(10) Development of understanding of biology and chemistry

In the modelling of acute toxicological endpoints, much has been gained regarding mechanisms of action. For many modelling approaches, it may be assumed that compounds fitting the same QSAR are acting by the same mechanism of action. This has allowed workers to define the chemical domain of certain mechanisms. There are countless examples where knowledge of biology and chemistry has been advanced by modelling in the field of toxicological and fate effects¹².

2.2. Global scenario of application of SAR and QSAR in toxicological hazard and risk assessment of chemicals and pharmaceuticals

Currently the toxic potential of large quantities of industrial chemicals including pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, pesticides and other synthetic or semi-synthetic chemicals is often required to be assessed by using standard animal models, comprising the basic test protocol for risk assessments for their approval as a registered product to launch into the market. With increasing concern about the environmental pollution and human health, the manufacture, storage, distribution and release of these xenobiotic substances after their use to the environment are controlled and regulated at local, national and international levels by different governments and regulatory agencies worldwide.

Due to absence of adequate experimental data of environmental fate, ecological effects and health effects of chemicals, several Government organizations have been applying the approaches of analogues, Structure-Activity Relationships (SARs) and Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationships (QSARs) to develop the predictions of untested compounds.

As a result of increasing chemicals uses, applications of analogues, SARs and QSARs by global Government organizations have increased. Australia, Canada, European countries (Denmark, Germany, The Netherlands), Japan, Russia and United States Government organizations largely rely on the approaches of analogues, SARs and QSARs to predict physical and chemical properties, environmental fate, ecological effects and health effects of organic chemicals and pharmaceuticals.

There are four main areas where QSARs may be applied by governmental regulatory agencies :

- (i) Prioritization of existing chemicals for further testing or assessment
- (ii) Classification and labelling of new chemicals
- (iii) Risk assessment of new and existing chemicals
- (iv) More importantly filling of data gaps

In recent time, QSARs have also been widely used by pharmaceutical companies and pesticide manufacturers to design biologically active chemicals. The QSAR tool has been applied by the governing and regulatory authorities to prioritize untested chemicals for more exhaustive and costly experimental evaluations. Applications of analogues, SAR and QSAR of different chemicals are also providing useful information in a regulatory decision making context in the absence of experimental data¹³⁻¹⁵.

3. Government organizations of different countries and their adaptation of SAR and QSAR in environmental toxicity prediction of chemicals and adverse health effects of chemicals and pharmaceuticals

3.1. The United States

The US Environmental Protection Agency's (US EPA) applications of QSARs include : (1) screening new chemical Pre-Manufacture Notifications (PMNs) for aquatic toxicity potential, (2) prioritizing chemicals for risk assessments and (3) predicting estrogen Receptor Binding Affinities¹⁶. In 1979, the US EPA's Office of Pollution Prevention and Toxics established a program to use SARs and QSARs in combination with expert opinions to predict the ecological and health effects of new chemicals for PMNs. The US EPA has 90 days to evaluate new chemical PMNs for which there are no requirements to submit toxicity data. In the absence of toxicity data, the

US EPA uses QSARs to predict aquatic toxicity of PMNs (http://www.epa.gov/OSA/spc/toxicitytesting/docs/toxtest_strategy_032309.pdf). A list of QSARs applied by the US EPA and the Interagency Testing Committee (ITC) to predict physical and chemical properties and environmental toxicity parameters is available at <http://www.epa.gov/oppt/exposure/docs/episuitedl.htm>. In Table 1, existing Government organizations in US and their application of analogues, SAR and QSAR in predicting environmental toxicity, physical and chemical properties and adverse health effects to human are mentioned.

3.2. Europe

In 2006, the European Parliament introduced legislation for a new chemical management system called Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH), intended to harmonize the information requirements applied to New and Existing Chemicals (Commission of the European Communities). In the European Union, the use of *in silico* methods is explicitly encouraged and even required in the REACH regulation⁴, which came into force from 1st June 2007. This regulation aims, among other things, at identifying, evaluating and regulating “*Persistent, Bioaccumulating and Toxic substances (PBT)*” effectively. To this end, it provides criteria⁴ for identifying such chemicals and “*Very Persistent and Very Bioaccumulative chemicals (vPvB)*”. In addition, the REACH regulation recommends the use of valid (Q)SARs for predicting the environmental and toxicological properties of chemicals, in the interests of time- and cost-effectiveness and animal welfare. The need to use *in silico* and other types of alternative (non-animal) methods (e.g. *in vitro* tests) has led to the development and implementation of Integrated Testing Strategies based as far as possible on the integrated use of non-animal data^{17,18}.

REACH aims to provide toxicity information for about 30000 out of the more than 100000 chemicals listed on the European Inventory of Existing Commercial Chemical Substances (EINECS), for which there is insufficient toxicological information on their hazardous properties. Within REACH, there are requirements to use sufficiently validated computational prediction models based on QSAR to fill in the toxicity data gaps, and thus save time, money and help to reduce the numbers of animals used for ex-

perimental testing purposes⁴. Guidelines for QSAR model development and validation proposed by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) are expected to help increase the acceptability of QSAR models for regulatory purposes¹⁹. QSARs can be applied to High Production Volume (HPV) chemicals under the Screening Information Data Set (SIDS) program to predict aquatic toxicity and log K_{ow} (Table 1) in OECD programs [<http://www.epa.gov/oppinr/chemtest/oecdside.htm>].

3.2.1. Denmark

In Danish EPA, QSAR is used for identification of PBT substances of around 166000 chemicals. The application of different approaches for predictions is mentioned in Table 1. These data can be used for self classification of around 20000 chemicals based on QSAR²⁰.

3.2.2. Germany

Environmental toxicity of new chemicals is assessed by the Umweltbundesamt (UBA), the Environmental Federal Agency which is a Government organization. For the prediction of local corrosive/irritant properties of chemicals (Table 1), the Federal Institute for Health Protection of Consumers and Veterinary Medicine (BgVV) developed a rule-based decision support system (DSS)^{21,22}.

3.2.3. The Netherlands

For the prediction of chemical toxicity and their properties (Table 1), SAR and QSAR are used by National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM). RIVM also apply analogues for prediction of hazardous health effects of chemicals²¹.

3.3. Australia

National Industrial Chemicals Notification and Assessment Scheme (NICNAS) predicts aquatic toxicity by analogues, and QSAR is used for the assessment of octanol-water partition coefficient (log K_{ow}) for new industrial chemicals. The approach of analogues is used in adverse health effects predictions. Effects are mentioned in Table 1.

3.4. Canada

Canadian Environmental Protection Act (CEPA) was amended in 1999. CEPA applies SAR for the prediction

Table 1. Representative list of various countries and their respective Government organizations, acts or schemes which consider application of analogues, SAR and QSAR for predicting toxicity properties of chemicals and pharmaceuticals on environment, human, animal and living systems

Country	Government Organization/ Scheme/Act	Applying method to predict physical and chemical properties, ecological and aquatic toxicity of chemicals		Applying method to predict adverse health effects of chemicals to human		Ref.	
		Analogues	SAR	QSAR	SAR		QSAR
The United States	US Air Force	-	-	$\log K_{ow}$, K_{oc} , BP, MP, VP, WS, HLC, Atm Ox	ADME, Acute, Irr, Sens, Derm	ADME, Acute, Carc	http://www.epa.gov/OSA/spc/toxicitytesting/docs/toxtest_strategy_032309.pdf
	Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry (ATSDR)	-	-	$\log K_{ow}$	-	Dev, Mut, Carc	http://www.epa.gov/oppt/exposure/docs/episuitedl.htm
	US Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA)	Biodeg	Biodeg	Aqua, $\log K_{ow}$, K_{oc} , BP, MP, VP, WS, HLC, Atm Ox, Hydrol, BCF	ADME, Acute, Irr, Sens, Sub/Chr, Rep, Dev, Mut, Carc	ADME, Acute, Irr, Sens, Sub/Chr, Rep, Dev, Mut, Carc	RBA
	Toxic Substances Control Act (TSCA) Interagency Testing Committee (ITC)	Biodeg	Biodeg	Aqua, $\log K_{ow}$, K_{oc} , BP, MP, VP, WS, HLC, Atm Ox, Hydrol, BCF	Acute, Rep, Carc	Acute Rep, Carc	-
	National Oceanic Atmospheric Administration (NOAA)	-	$\log K_{ow}$	-	-	-	-
	Consumer Product Safety Commission (CPSC)	-	-	-	Derm	Derm	-
	Food and Drug Administration (FDA)	-	-	-	-	-	Carc
	National Cancer Institute (NCI)	-	-	-	Carc	Carc	Carc

Table-1 (contd.)

National Toxicology Program (NTP)	-	-	-	Mut, Carc	-
Australia National Industrial Chemicals Notification and Assessment Scheme (NICNAS)	Aqua	-	log K_{ow}	Acute, Irr, Sens, Derm, Sub/Chr, Mut	21
Canada Canadian Environmental Protection Act (CEPA)	-	Biodeg	Aqua, log K_{ow} , K_{oc} , BCF	-	24
European countries European Economic Commission (EEC), Organization for Economic Cooperation Development (OECD)	-	-	Aqua, log K_{ow} , K_{oc} , Atm Ox, Biodeg	-	4, 17, 18
Danish EPA (Denmark) Umweltbundesamt (UBA), the Environmental Federal Agency (Germany)	-	-	Aqua, log K_{ow} , K_{oc} , Biodeg, BCF	Acute, Irr, Sens, Derm, Rep. Dev, Mut, Carc	20
National Institute for Public Health and Environment (RIVM) (The Netherlands)	-	-	Aqua, Biodeg	Irr, Sens	21, 24
Japan Chemical Substances Control Law	-	BCF	Aqua, log K_{ow} , K_{oc} , BCF	Irr, Sens, Derm, Sub/Chr, Rep, Dev, Mut	21
	-	-	-	-	25

Here, Aqua = Aquatic toxicity, log K_{ow} = logarithm of the octanol-water partition coefficient, K_{oc} = Sediment or soil organic carbon partition coefficient, BP = Boiling point, MP = Melting point, VP = Vapour pressure, WS = Water solubility, HLC = Henry's Law Constant, Atm Ox = Atmospheric oxidation, Biodeg = Biodegradation, Hydrol = Hydrolysis, BCFs = Bioconcentration factors of chemicals.
 ADME = Absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion; Acute = Acute toxicity, Irr = Skin or eye irritation. Sens = Skin or respiratory sensitization, Derm = Precutaneous or dermal absorption, Sub/Chr = Subchronic or chronic toxicity, Rep = Reproductive toxicity, Dev = Developmental toxicity, Mut = Mutagenicity, Carc = Carcinogenicity, RBA = Estrogen or androgen receptor binding affinity of chemicals and pharmaceuticals.

of biodegradation of Domestic Substance List (DSL) chemicals (Table 1). To assist in the categorization process, a technical advisory group (TAG) was constituted. This comprised a range of experts to advice on matters relating to structure-based prediction of toxicity and fate. Environment Canada was also recently funded a study to assess and evaluate six modelling packages to predict acute toxicity, with particular application to prioritizing chemicals within the Canadian DSL²³. The six packages assessed were Syracuse Research Corporation program to predict environmental toxicities (ECOSAR), TOxicity Prediction by Komputer-Assisted Technology (TOPKAT), a probabilistic neural network (PNN), a computational neural network (CNN), the QSAR components of the ASTER system, and the OASIS system²⁴.

3.5. Russia

Registers of chemical substances in Russia are databases where chemicals are collected and registered. The major registers are National register of pesticides and agrochemicals; National register of potentially hazardous chemical and biological substances; National register of human and veterinary medicinal products; National register on waste disposal facilities and federal classification catalogue of wastes; Regional Toxicological Information Center "TOXI", St-Petersburg. Russian register of potentially hazardous chemical and biological substances in Moscow, Russia includes on-line database which contains information about 2977 substances (Russian National registers of potentially hazardous chemical and biological substances). The database HAZARD includes data on teratogenicity, carcinogenicity and mutagenicity of chemicals (Database HAZARD). Different QSAR models and expert systems are used in recent times for toxicity prediction of chemicals and hazardous materials.

3.6. Japan

In Japan, Bioconcentration factors (BCF) are measured for new chemicals under Chemical Substances Control Law. Chemical Substances Council advises the Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry (METI) during assessment of new chemicals. If a substance has octanol-water partition coefficient $\log K_{ow} < 3$, than BCF need not be assessed (Metallic, ionisable and surface active substances are excluded)²⁵.

3.7. India

In response to the REACH programme, the Ministry of Chemicals & Fertilizers in conjunction with the Indian Chemical Manufacturers Association (ICMA) has formed special task forces. The first task force looks at the framework needed by India to respond to the global regulatory programs. The second task force looks at the development of GLP laboratories throughout India. The third task force seeks to develop India as a hub for IT-based Services under REACH. The vision of the task forces is to help India meet and capitalize on the advantage of developing IT-based services under Global Regulatory Programs such as REACH, including the promotion and development of QSAR models, by co-ordination and development of the expert capabilities in the country. The IT Task Force released a White paper in 2005 which looks at the need and opportunity to use QSAR to estimate the value of unknown physical, chemical, biological and environmental properties of chemicals based on known or computationally accessible properties, as may be relevant to Global Environmental Regulatory Programs such as the REACH program of the European Union (http://chemicals.nic.in/white_paper_qsar.pdf).

There is no doubt about widespread use by regulatory authorities of QSARs and computer-based approaches to predict toxicity and fate. This approach is largely used in the US, but also increasingly in Canada and the EU. Due to desire to obtain more information regarding the deleterious effects of chemicals to the environment and man, it is likely that these approaches will be used more often. Most regulatory uses of QSARs are for warning purposes. Considerably greater efforts should be used to validate predictions of toxicity and fate to increase confidence in the use of these techniques.

In Table 1 we figure out different countries and their respective Government organizations, acts or schemes which consider application of analogues, SAR and QSAR for predicting toxicity properties of chemicals and pharmaceuticals on environment, human, animal and living systems.

4. Toxicity : multidimensional facets

Toxicity has many dimensions. A harmful chemical may cause functional or anatomical damage, irreversible change in homeostasis or increased susceptibility to other

chemicals or biological stress, including infectious diseases. In case of immune reactions leading to hypersensitivity or allergic effects, the first exposure to the causative agent may not produce any adverse effect, although it sensitizes the organism to respond adversely to future exposures, often at a very low level. The amount of exposure to a chemical required to produce injury varies over a very wide range depending on the chemical and the form in which it occurs. The rapid expansion of the world's population, combined with industrial progress, has made a significant impact of chemicals including pharmaceuticals on the world's ecosystems. Since human society depends on so many types and classes of chemicals, it is very important to know the way in which the chemicals interact with the environment. The important classes of chemicals with high impacts on the environment are as follows : metals, halogenated hydrocarbons, and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, medical and veterinary drugs, pesticides, agrochemicals, synthetic and semi-synthetic chemicals and dyes²⁶.

In this report, for discussion, we have classified toxicity into two classes : (1) toxicity due to chemicals (environmental toxicity and toxicity on exposure) and (2) toxicity due to consumed pharmaceuticals.

4.1. Chemical toxicity

Chemicals are able to bring about both desirable and undesirable effects on organisms to which they are exposed, and the actions of medicines and poisons and toxic agents have been recognized for thousands of years. As a

result of industrialization, modern man and the environment are now exposed to increasing numbers of chemicals. Because of their potential hazard, there is an appreciation of the requirement to assess the effects of these chemicals.

Due to existence of high number of untested chemicals, chemical toxicity has emerged as a global problem in recent times. In Table 2, we grouped some major hazardous chemicals which are largely responsible for the nuisance. Mentioned chemicals have direct effect on environment and human systems²⁷.

According to the Toxic Substances Control Act (TSCA), the new chemicals should have data for the toxicologically relevant properties which are mentioned in Table 3²⁸.

4.1.1. Environmental toxicity by chemicals

Our modern industrial society is highly dependent on different chemical entities such as the fertilizers and pesticides used in the production of food, pharmaceuticals (i.e. drugs and materials used in medicine and health care and cosmetic products), industrial and household products^{29,30}. Uses of these chemicals without proper ecotoxicological information can lead to the dangerous situation of the global environment. These chemicals either directly or indirectly by producing metabolic and/or degraded bi-products severely affect the aquatic species of the environment and human health.

Environmental contaminants like lead and polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) are usually found in food and

Table 2. Representative list of different hazardous chemicals and pharmaceuticals and their grouping methods

Hazardous chemicals and pharmaceuticals	Grouping methods
EDC (Endocrine Disrupting Chemical)	Toxicological mode of action or endpoint
CMR (Carcinogenic, Mutagenic, toxic to Reproduction)	Toxicological mode of action or endpoint
PBT (Persistent, Bioaccumulative Toxic)	Environmental properties (e.g. ease of degradation or fat solubility)
vPvB (very Persistent, very Bioaccumulative)	Environmental properties (e.g. ease of degradation or fat solubility)
POP (Persistent Organic Pollutant)	Environmental properties (e.g. ease of degradation or fat solubility)
PPCPs (Pharmaceuticals and Personal Care Products)	Type of intended usage
Priority pollutants and other regulated pollutants	Legislative enactment
Xenobiotics, exotics	Foreign versus endogenous
Toxicants, toxins, toxics	Overall toxicity
Emerging - contaminants/pollutants	Novelty or new concern
HPV (High Production Volume chemicals)	Quantity (manufactured/imported in US in annual amounts > 1 million pounds)

Table 3. Representative list of types of toxicological properties and different parameters

Types of toxicological property	Parameters	
Physicochemical	Molar volume	
	Boiling point	
	Melting point	
	Vapour pressure	
	Aqueous solubility	
	Dissociation constant	
	Partition coefficient	
	Reactivity (electrophile)	
	Biological	Receptor binding (K_d)
		Michaelis constant
Inhibitor constant		
Biodegradation		
Bioconcentration		
Alkylation profile		
Metabolic profile		
Chronic toxicity		
Carcinogenicity		
Mutagenicity		
	Acute toxicity (LD_{50}/LC_{50})	

human tissues³¹. The mixtures of Persistent, Bio-accumulative and Toxic (PBT) chemicals released after their use are potentially harmful when they accumulate in the living body or the environment. Due to their persistence and bio-accumulative potential of the chemicals, these chemical pollutants tend to severely change the ecosystem and produce neuro, reproductional and immuno toxicities on human, wildlife and aquatic organisms situated in the different levels of food chain³². When environmental factors cause an array of troubling symptoms, they can also be attributed to a condition termed 'multiple chemical sensitivity' or MCS (also known as chemical injury, chemical sensitivity, environmental illness, and multiple allergy). MCS also known as toxic injury can cause asthma, chest pains, and hives among other symptoms. Knowing the causes and sources of toxicity can also help us to find alternatives to conventional methods and resources in order to avoid MCS (<http://www.epa.gov/risk/index.htm>).

4.1.1.1. Estuarine sediment acute toxicity

Sediment toxicity is largely caused by organic contaminants (PAHs, PCBs, DDT metabolites and γ -HCH).

Sediment bioassays are a powerful tool for the study of sediment toxicity and are recommended along with others methodologies to classify and prioritise areas of contaminated sediments. Amphipods (*Corophium multisetosum*) stock has been shown to be sensitive to contaminated sediments and to disappear from benthic communities impacted by pollution and reappear under recovery conditions³³.

4.1.1.2. Aquatic (water) toxicity

Industrialization and release of increasing number of toxic organic chemicals are deteriorating the aquatic environment. Leakage of toxic compounds results from process equipment failure and lack of proper pollution prevention and maintenance measures. Heavy metal release into the environment has occurred continuously through acid mine drainage (AMD), and it is a severe water pollution problem associated with mining activity. High concentrations of trace metals and acidic pHs have been known to affect adversely aquatic ecosystems. Acid mine drainage is highly acidic and contain high concentrations of iron and other potentially toxic heavy metals such as Cd, Cu, Pb and Zn³⁴.

4.1.1.3. Effects on freshwater zooplankton

Surface water bodies are contaminated with many anthropogenic toxic chemicals that can affect their natural communities. It is necessary to assess the effects of these chemicals in order to conserve aquatic ecosystems. Among the anthropogenic chemicals, pesticides may cause the most serious problems because they are designed specifically to kill organisms. Surface water bodies are contaminated with many anthropogenic toxic chemicals that can affect their natural communities. It is necessary to assess the effects of these chemicals in order to conserve aquatic ecosystems. Toxicity is shown to vary depending on animal species, genotype, life stage, and size at birth. Natural stresses such as food shortage, oxygen depletion and odours of potential predators can also affect toxicity. The following patterns are recognized as effects of pesticides at the community and ecosystem levels : (1) induction of dominance by small species; (2) an increase of species richness and diversity; and (3) elongation of the food chain and reduction of energy transfer efficiency from primary producers to top predators³⁵.

4.1.1.4. Bioaccumulation, bioconcentration and biotransformation

If we are to quantify the risks that environmental pollution poses, we need an understanding of the many factors that affect the distribution of a chemical in the environment. Connell wrote a comprehensive review of the bioaccumulation of xenobiotic compounds³⁶. For regulatory purposes, bioaccumulation factors are often used to assess the uptake of both new and existing chemicals by organisms. Bioconcentration of chemicals in aquatic organism, water and air are very alarming issue right now³⁶. A large number of chemicals that resist the degradation in the environment accumulate in body tissues and are intrinsically toxic to organisms in the environment or to humans. The possible effects of long-term and cumulative exposure to such chemicals are not always adequately reflected in risk assessment methods evaluating acute toxicity and short-term exposure. Thus, bioconcentration is of great concern when defining toxic effects due to chronic exposure³⁴. Chemical bioconcentration is usually expressed as a bioconcentration factor (BCF), which can be defined as the ratio of the concentration of chemical present in an aquatic organism to that in the environment³⁷. REACH regulation states that a substance is identified as bioaccumulative (B) when the BCF is higher than 2000 ($\log \text{BCF} > 3.301$) and very bioaccumulative (vB) if it is higher than 5000 ($\log \text{BCF} > 3.699$)⁴.

4.1.1.5. Soil erosion

Sorption of a chemical (usually from water) by soil may cause soil erosion. Soil erosion by chemicals is a global problem. It is necessary to have knowledge of the ways in which a chemical can be distributed in the soil environment³⁸.

4.1.2. Human toxicity by chemicals

To live in the 21st century means to live in a toxic world where we are exposed daily to numerous environmental toxins and pollutants which find their way into our air, water, and the soil in which we grow our food. We spend our days inhaling pollutants such as car fumes and cigarette smoke. We drink water that has been thoroughly treated with chemicals, and eat food that is grown in toxic soil, pumped with hormones, and packaged with preservatives. While our livers, kidneys, skin and lym-

phatic systems work around the clock to eliminate these dangerous toxins from our body, they very often just cannot keep up. The result is a build up of poisons in the system which destroys body tissue, damage organs, depress the immune system, and leave the door open to a number of serious illnesses (<http://www.epa.gov/risk/index.htm>). Human exposure to industrial effluents has led to health effects ranging from headaches, lung and skin irritations, and nausea to various disabilities and serious impairments of liver and neurological function. Regardless of the manufacturing process employed, effluent from industries, such as, organic chemical industry, textile and dye industry, pulp and paper industry and petroleum refineries, are characterized by the co-existence of hundreds of toxic chemicals, specifically hydrophobic organic compounds (HOCs)³⁹. Major toxic effects by chemicals to human and living systems are described as follows :

4.1.2.1. Prenatal developmental/reproductive toxicity

One of the primary chemical toxicity is developmental toxicity which is characterized by maternal effects and foetal endpoints including malformations, resorptions, and fetal weight reduction. The primary expressions of developmental toxicity are fetal weight reduction, skeletal variations and abnormalities, and fetal urogenital defects. Developmental toxicity refers to adverse effects produced by an exposure proceeding to conception, or during pregnancy and childhood. Assessing disruptions in embryogenesis involves testing pregnant laboratory animals of two species, typically rats and rabbits, exposed during the period of major organogenesis and evaluated just before term along with monitoring maternal status throughout pregnancy. Under this design, the major manifestations of developmental toxicity may express as one or more of a number of possible endpoints such as intrauterine death, fetal growth retardation, structural variations and abnormalities. Predictive modelling of developmental toxicity requires a computational framework that can integrate mechanistic data with high-quality toxicity data from *in vivo* studies⁴⁰. Reproductive toxicity is used to describe the adverse effects induced (by chemicals) on sexual function and fertility in adult males and females. There is a public concern with regard to effects from reproductive toxicants to humans. In particular, impair-

ment of the ability to reproduce and the occurrence of reproductive disorders are highly sensitive issues. In order to identify reproductive toxicants, a number of tests are required for regulatory purposes⁴¹.

4.1.2.2. Mammalian systemic toxicity

Acute toxicity, subchronic toxicity and chronic toxicity are involved in systemic toxicity. The information from systemic toxicity studies is used in hazard assessment and the risk management of the chemicals. Under the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) legislation of the EU, information on acute toxicity is required for substances manufactured and imported in quantities of 1 ton or more⁴².

4.1.2.3. Carcinogenicity

Under REACH, the need for a two-year carcinogenicity assay for chemicals produced at >1000 metric tons per year will be determined on a case-by-case basis. Widespread use and frequent or prolonged human exposure combined with evidence of mutagenicity or induction of hyperplastic/preneoplastic lesions in repeat-dose toxicity studies will trigger the need for an assessment of carcinogenic potential for high production volume (HPV) chemicals which are largely and frequently used or for which prolonged human exposure occur. There are certain evidences of carcinogenicity and genotoxicity due to these chemicals⁴³.

Short-term tests are currently used to predict a chemical's ability to induce cancer. These tests were implemented based on scientific evidence that emerged in the 1970's linking DNA damage and mutation with cancer. The main reason behind the screening methodologies to identify genotoxicants [e.g. as described in Harmonization of Technical Requirements for Registration of Pharmaceuticals for Human Use guidance (International Conference on Harmonization Guidance for industry)] is on the basis that such agents would most likely pose cancer risk in humans. Environmental toxicants have not been regulated as carcinogens on the basis of positive genotoxicity results alone. However, chemicals testing positive in standard genotoxicity assays are generally supposed to contribute to cancer induction via a genotoxic or mutagenic mode of action⁴⁴.

4.1.2.4. Immunotoxicity

Immunotoxicity is defined as detrimental effects that chemicals may have on the immune system. It can be directly or indirectly induced in various ways. Direct immunotoxicity is expressed as immunosuppression or immunostimulation. On the other hand indirect immunotoxicity is mainly expressed as immunohypersensitivity or autoimmunity. The latter one is not caused by the direct effects of the compounds on components of the immune system, but relatively by immune responses to the chemical or to self-determinants altered by the chemical. Immune system has a central role in maintaining health and it comprises many biological activities. Therefore, if it is affected by chemicals then immunotoxicity results⁴⁵.

The International Collaborative Immunotoxicity Study (ICICIS) was established in 1986. It works jointly with the International Programme on Chemical Safety (a cooperative programme of the United Nations Environment Programme, the International Labour Office and the World Health Organization), the Commission of the European Union and the United Kingdom Department of Health. The objectives were to examine the general indicators of immunotoxicity⁴⁶.

4.1.2.5. Neurotoxicity

Neurotoxicity considers that chemicals agitate neurological functions by interfering with the structure or function of neurones. Developmental neurotoxicity involves alterations in behaviour, neurohistology, neurochemistry, neurophysiology, and gross dysmorphology of the central nervous system (CNS) due to chemical exposure of the mother during pregnancy or during lactation. Based on published information, at least 138 industrial chemicals were rated as neurotoxic to humans. Clinical signs and symptoms such as addiction, ataxia, coma, and delirium : hallucinations, muscle fasciculation, narcosis, organic psychosyndrome, paralysis, paraesthesia, parkinsonism, peripheral neuropathy, and tremors occur due to neurotoxicity⁴⁷.

The US-EPA has recently required the registrants to conduct developmental neurotoxicity studies for a number of neurotoxic pesticides⁴⁸. In EU, the SCF (Scientific Committee for Food) has recommended that appropriate

experts should address this issue with the view to setting criteria to decide when developmental neurotoxicity studies in the future are necessary⁴⁹. Until recently, however, developmental neurotoxicity testing of industrial chemicals has not been a clear regulatory requirement in the EU, probably partly due to the lack of an accepted OECD TG. The revised EU Technical Guidance Document for Risk Assessment (EU-TGD) has now included the OECD draft TG 426 in the testing strategy for new and existing substances, and biocides⁵⁰. In Table 4 neurotoxicants for human are mentioned.

Table 4. Representative list of neurotoxicants for human

Pesticides	Aldrin, Chlordane, DDT, 2,4-D, Dialifos, Dinoseb, Endosulfan, Endothion, Endrin, Fenthion, Fonofos, Dimefox, Dieldrin etc.
Organic solvents and industrial chemicals	Acrylamide, Allyl chloride, Carbon disulphide, Chloroform, Toluene, Ethanol, Methanol, Methoxyethanol, Methyl chloride, Phenol etc.

4.1.2.6. Respiratory toxicity

In the last 15 years it has become obvious that the rodent nasal cavity is an important target organ for toxicity. It is due to that wide variety of compounds including environmental contaminants⁵¹ and industrial chemicals⁵² have been shown to cause nasal lesions or tumours in experimental animals. Chemical warfare nerve agents (CWNA) like soman, sarin, cyclosarin, and tabun are potent inhibitors of cholinesterases, especially acetylcholinesterase (AChE), which hydrolyzes acetylcholine at cholinergic synapses. Inhibition of AChE leads to acetylcholine (ACh) accumulation at synapses and hyperstimulation of post-synaptic cholinergic receptors. Respiratory disturbances play a central role in CWNA-induced toxicity and respiratory failure is the common cause of death following exposure⁵³. Anzueto *et al.*⁵⁴ have reported apnea, hypoxia, and respiratory disturbances following inhalation exposure to soman and sarin in baboons.

4.1.2.7. Nephrotoxicity

Due to unique physiological properties, kidney is an important organ for drug-induced toxicity. Urinary pH changes occurring in renal acid-base regulation together with disproportionately large blood supply to kidney may result in increased xenobiotic accumulation in the kidney

compared to other tissues. Drug metabolizing enzymes are present in kidneys which can biotransform inert chemicals to highly reactive chemicals. These are CYP450 dependent mixed function oxidases, prostaglandin endoperoxide synthetase, glutathione-S-transferase, aminopeptidase, sulphotransferase, N-acetyltransferase as well as uridine diphosphate and uridine diphosphate glucuronosyltransferase. The unequal distribution of these enzymes indicates kidney as a major organ for drug-induced toxicity. Here, in Table 5 we give different types of nephrotoxicity and example of one drug each for every type of toxicity⁵⁵.

Table 5. Different types of nephrotoxicity, and representative list of drugs involved in respective toxicity

Type of nephrotoxicity	Drugs involved
Tubular injury	Aminoglycosides
Acute interstitial nephritis	Methicillin
Decreased renal perfusion	Cyclosporin
Primary glomerulopathy	D-Penicillamine
Obstructive nephropathy	Methoxyflurane

4.1.2.8. Endocrine disruption

The prediction of the ability of chemicals to cause endocrine disruption has also been addressed by the EPA. In 1996, the Office of Pollution Prevention and Toxics (OPPT) established the Endocrine Disruptors Screening and Testing Advisory Committee (EDSTAC). The EDSTAC developed a conceptual framework to screen and test chemicals for endocrine disruption. As a part of this, the Endocrine Disruptor Priority Setting Database (EDPSD1) was developed. In the pharmaceutical industry for drug discovery and in toxicology and environmental science for risk assessment, testing for endocrine disruption of chemicals are essential. EDPSD2 is a decision support tool that is used to select chemicals for endocrine disruption screening assays⁵⁶.

4.1.2.9. Skin sensitization

Skin sensitization is a significant environmental and occupational health concern causing a major problem for individuals, for employers and for marketing certain products. Consequently there exists an important need to identify accurately chemicals that have the potential to cause skin sensitization. Sensitization is also an endpoint that

requires assessment under the new European Union (EU) REACH programme. Current assessment of skin sensitization still relies on animal tests. Guinea pigs have been the species of choice for predictive sensitization tests for many years; however, under REACH, the test of first choice is now the mouse Local Lymph Node Assay (LLNA). A reduced version of the LLNA (rLLNA) using only the equivalent of the high dose group from the full LLNA can be used as a screening test to distinguish between sensitizers and non-sensitizers⁵⁷.

4.1.2.10. Skin irritation and corrosion

Another important skin related toxicity of chemicals is skin irritation and corrosion. Validated alternative methods accepted for regulatory use determining skin corrosion exist that have replaced the respective animal tests. The validation of two methods for the testing of skin irritation, EPISKIN[®] and EpiDerm[®], has been finalised and scientifically accepted by ECVAM Scientific Advisory Committee (ESAC) in Spring 2007. The EPISKIN[®] method is foreseen to replace completely the regulatory Draize skin irritation test whereas the EpiDerm[®] model is seen as a constituent of a testing strategy. Other aspects such as reversibility of irritation and dose-response characteristics, important components for risk assessment, have yet to be addressed. Further information is available at the ECVAM website (<http://ecvam.jrc.it/index.htm> section news, events and meetings).

New Chemicals Database for chemicals notified in the EU, a decision support system for skin corrosion/irritation potential in terms of C&L has been developed and validated consisting of two predictive tools : (1) physico-chemical exclusion rules (cut-off-values) to identify chemicals with no skin irritation/corrosion potential and (2) inclusion rules to identify chemicals with skin irritation/corrosion potential by use of structural alerts of chemicals. Furthermore, a Skin Irritation Corrosion Rule Estimation Tool (SICRET) has been developed which is a user-friendly tool that enables non-QSAR experts to identify chemicals with or without skin corrosion or irritation potential based on physicochemical properties or structural alerts⁵⁸. Chemicals and pharmaceuticals are associated with different mechanisms of action when creating the problems of skin irritation and corrosion⁵⁹.

Skin irritation may be mediated by :

- (i) Reaction with skin proteins and lipids by surface active agents.
- (ii) Dissolution of skin lipids by low-molecular-weight organic chemicals.

Skin corrosion may be associated with :

- (i) Erosion of the stratum corneum by inorganic acids/bases and by strong organic acids with pH <2 and bases with pH >11.5.
- (ii) Binding by cationic substances including surfactants, quaternary ammonium salts and sulphonium ions.

4.1.2.11. Eye irritation and corrosion

One of the most sensitive organs is eye. Due to large exposure of chemicals, gas and fumes, eye irritation and corrosion is a major toxicity for human system. The regulatory authorities of EU recommend different tests for the identification and classification of severe eye irritants. In Spring 2007, two of these tests, the Bovine Corneal Opacity and Permeability (BCOP) and the Isolated Chicken Eye (ICE) test methods were validated and scientifically accepted by ESAC⁶⁰.

4.2. Toxicity by pharmaceuticals

Major toxicity of pharmaceuticals is drug-induced adverse effects to human. The importance of optimizing molecules during early stages of drug development is not only for efficacy but also for avoiding undesirable pharmacokinetic and toxicological properties. It is the fine balance of target potency, selectivity, favourable ADME (absorption distribution metabolism excretion) and (pre)-clinical safety properties that will ultimately lead to the selection and clinical development of a potential new drug. The typical compound entering a Phase-I clinical trial has undergone years of rigorous preclinical testing but still only has an 8% chance of reaching the market⁶¹. Therefore, it is quite clear that discharge of large number of dropout pharmaceuticals in the later stage collectively contribute to environment toxicity. Drug-induced toxicity to human and toxicity of released pharmaceuticals to the environment have emerged as the major toxicity problems of pharmaceuticals.

4.2.1. Environmental toxicity by pharmaceuticals

The most significant entry routes for pharmaceuticals

into the environment are via urine and faeces of the patients, discharge of pharmaceuticals such as antibiotics along with other compounds used as growth promoters in livestock⁶² during intense farming, from manufacture and leachate from landfill sites where expired, unwanted or spoiled drugs have been disposed of in household waste⁶³, with household garbage⁶³. Other sources include direct application in aqua farming, manure run-off, run-off from the application of sewage sludge and manure on farmland as fertilizers, via hospital effluent or, finally, via landfill leaching⁶⁴. Reviewing the available published reports and scientific publications, it is revealed that acute toxic effects of pharmaceutical substances on various types of organisms in environment are due to their persistent, bio-accumulative and toxic effects. The growing concern over the release of pharmaceutically active compounds used by humans or veterinary medicines⁶⁵ and personal care products into waste water, air and soil of the environment has prompted the introduction of risk assessment guidelines in the European Union by the European Medicines Evaluation Agency (EMA) and in the United States by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and other countries. Pharmaceuticals like oestrogens have been found in plasticisers, pesticides and preservatives while 17 α -ethinyloestradiol (EE2) used as a component of contraceptive pill⁶⁶, antibiotics, disinfectants, clofibrate (a lipid lowering agent) have been identified in ground and tap water samples⁶⁷.

The antiepileptic drug carbamazepine, one of the most persistent pharmaceuticals, has been detected in the environment⁶⁸. Zwiener and Frimmel⁶⁹ have reported the presence of analgesics in municipal sewage treatment plant. The cardiovascular drug propranolol has been reported downstream from the sewage treatment plant. The quantities of several of these compounds used throughout the world are comparable to agrochemicals (Daughton and Ternes, 1999)⁷⁰. Actual used amounts are highly variable depending on location, demographics, and season. Huge amount of antibiotics are produced in the US each year, of which a major part is used in agriculture/farming⁷¹. In the EU, large amount of antibiotics is administered to farm animals and to humans⁷². Other highly used classes are general analgesics with large amount consumed per year in Germany in 1997. Other high volume compounds in Germany in 1997 were the contrast media

iopromide, antiepileptic carbamazepine, cardiovascular compound bezafibrate. A relatively low tonnage, but high prescription rate and high concern compound is the contraceptive sex hormone 17 α -ethinyloestradiol^{4,60}. Directives by the EU for human and veterinary compounds⁷³ stipulate that an environmental risk assessment should be part of the approval procedure since 1998. Eco-toxicological data are available only for a few pharmaceuticals in the open peer-reviewed literature and eco-toxicological databases (ECETOX (EU) and ECOTOX (US))⁷⁴ and only a small number of new pharmaceuticals have been subjected to a complete risk assessment, including a battery of appropriate eco-toxicological tests in the EU⁶⁵. This is primarily due to low values of the predicted or measured environmental concentrations (PEC or MEC) as the cut-off value for triggering eco-toxicological risk assessment⁷⁴. The QSAR data may be the first step in gaining more general knowledge on this issue⁷⁵ as an alternative to non-animal method. The European Union Commission's scientific committee on toxicity, ecotoxicity and environment (CSTEE) has identified the need for a proactive approach in obtaining data on the environmental effects of pharmaceuticals. They noted that some pharmaceuticals are used in large volumes, have widespread use, and they are found in surface waters. Jones *et al.*⁷⁶ found that all top prescription pharmaceuticals in the UK exceeded the environmental risk assessment trigger value in surface waters, and may give rise to acute and chronic eco-toxicological effects in the aquatic environment, warranting environmental concern. Thus, it is recognized that a prioritization procedure needs to be developed for environmental risk assessment of pharmaceuticals, and that this should follow the general scheme for chemicals described in the White Paper for future EU chemicals policy^{4,15} i.e. REACH guideline, where the use of QSARs are stressed. Sanderson *et al.*⁷⁷ summarized and ranked relative hazards of 2848 pharmaceuticals indicating that there was large "within class" variability and that the cardiovascular class of pharmaceuticals potentially posed an environmental concern⁴. The four classes of special environmental feature-specific concerns, which are typically not assessed in traditional environmental toxicity testing under EU directive 1488/94⁷⁸ are antibiotics [resistance issue], antineoplastics [mutagenicity], sex hormones [endocrine disruption], and cardiovascular high

potential hazard^{4,60,74}, except for resistance in soil microbial communities for antibiotics⁷⁸. The CSTEE published a summary classification of available ecotoxicity data for pharmaceuticals used for human into five groups; however, that study consisted of a total of only 76 compounds and six metabolites, with only 18 studies containing information on chronic aquatic toxicity to *Daphnia magna*.

Antibiotics are used extensively in human and veterinary medicine, as well as in aquaculture, for the purpose of preventing (prophylaxis) or treating microbial infections. Several hundred different antibiotic and antimycotic substances are used in human and veterinary medicine, e.g. more than 250 in Germany⁷⁹. Wise *et al.*⁸⁰ estimated antibiotic consumption worldwide to lie between 100000 and 200000 tons per annum. In 1996, about 10200 tons of antibiotics were used in the EU, of which approximately 50% was applied in veterinary medicine and as growth promoters. According to data supplied by the European Federation of Animal Health⁸¹, in 1999 there were a total of 13216 tons of antibiotics used in the European Union and Switzerland, 65% of which was applied in human medicine. In the United States, one estimate is that 50% of the 22700 metric tons of all antimicrobials prescribed annually are for humans and 50% for use in animals, agriculture and aquaculture⁸².

It was found that β -lactam antibiotics, including the sub-groups of penicillins, cephalosporins and, as a marginal fraction carbapenems and others, make up the largest share of human-use antibiotics in most countries. They account for approximately 50–70% of total antibiotic use. In most countries, sulphonamides, macrolides, and fluoroquinolones follow in decreasing order of use (http://www.esac.ua.ac.be/main.aspx?c=*ESAC2&n=1063). Cars *et al.*⁸³ obtained data for non-hospital antibiotic sales for 1997 from the 15 member states and analysed these according to the Anatomic Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) classification system, and expressed them as defined daily doses (DDD) per 1000 people per day. Sales of antibiotics varied more than four-fold : France (36.5), Spain (32.4), Portugal (28.8), and Belgium (26.7) had the highest sales, whereas the Netherlands (8.9), Denmark (11.3), Sweden (13.5), Germany (13.6), and Austria (12.4) had the lowest. There was also great variation in the use of different classes of antibiotics. In another study (Vaccheri

et al., 2002), antibiotic consumption was 16.5 DDD/1000 inhabitants/day (DDD per 1000 inhabitants and day) in Ravenna (Italy) and 10.4 DDD/1000 inhabitants/day in Funen (Denmark). Antibiotics can reach the environment with the potential of adversely affecting aquatic and terrestrial organisms. It might reach humans again via drinking water. In general, the effects of antibacterial agents on bacteria and microalgae are found to be 2–3 orders of magnitude below the toxic values for higher trophic levels⁸⁴. Here, we mention major effects of antibiotics to the aquatic and marine ecology.

(1) Antibiotics present in Waste water and sewage system have the potential to affect the microbial community in sewage systems. The inhibition of waste water bacteria may seriously affect organic matter degradation; therefore, effects of antibacterial agents on the microbial population are of great interest⁸⁵.

(2) Surface water substances which are not or are only partly eliminated in the sewage treatment plant will reach surface water where they may affect organisms of different trophic levels. In a model aquatic system using synthetic fresh water, nitrifying bacteria were significantly affected by an aquaculture antibiotic. The disruption of the nitrification process already occurred in concentrations likely to be found in fish treatment tanks and sediments⁸⁶.

(3) Several reports have addressed the impacts of antibiotics on soil dwelling organisms. Antimicrobials may have qualitative and quantitative effects upon the resident microbial community found in sediment, which can in turn affect the degradation of organic matter. Furthermore, direct toxic effects upon the resident organisms cannot be excluded⁸⁷.

The major effects by different groups of pharmaceuticals are divided into two classes.

(a) *Acute effects* :

Pharmaceuticals are assessed for their acute toxicity by traditional standard tests according to established guidelines (e.g. OECD, U.S. EPA, ISO) using established laboratory organisms such as algae, zooplankton and other invertebrates and fish. Webb⁸⁸ noted that the most toxic classes were antidepressants, antibacterials and antipsychotics, but the range of responses within each of these categories was large, typically of several orders of magnitude.

(a.1) *Beta-blockers* :

Acute toxicity of beta-blockers is not extensively studied, with the exception of propranolol. This compound shows the highest acute toxicity and highest log K_{ow} as compared to other beta-blockers. This observation and the fact that it is a strong membrane stabilizer whereas other investigated beta-blockers are not may in part explain its higher toxicity⁸⁹.

(a.2) *Blood lipid lowering agents* :

Similar to beta-blockers, acute toxicity of lipid lowering agents is not extensively reported. Clofibrate showed LC_{50} values in the range of 7.7–39.7 mg/L and can be classified as harmful to aquatic organisms. The fish *Gambusia holbrooki* [LC_{50} (96 h) = 7.7 mg/L] seems the most sensitive organism to acute clofibrate concentrations studied so far⁹⁰.

(a.3) *Analgesics and non-steroidal antiinflammatory drugs (NSAIDs)* :

Diclofenac seems to be the compound having highest acute toxicity within the class of NSAIDs, since for all the tests performed, the effect concentrations were below 100 mg/L. Short-term acute toxicity was analysed in algae and invertebrates⁸⁸; phytoplankton was found to react more sensitively [lowest EC_{50} (96 h) = 14.5 mg/L] than zooplankton [lowest EC_{50} (96 h) = 22.43 mg/L]⁹¹.

(a.4) *Cytostatic compounds and cancer therapeutics* :

Acute toxicity of methotrexate on highly proliferative species, namely the ciliate *Tetrahymena pyriformis*, indicated acute effects [EC_{50} (48 h) = 45 mg/L]⁹². Teratogenicity in fish embryos was observed at even higher concentrations [EC_{50} (48 h) = 85 mg/L]. About 17% of the pharmaceuticals displayed an acute toxicity below 100 mg/L, and for fluoxetine, all toxicity values were below 10 mg/L⁹². On the other hand, 38% of the pharmaceuticals such as acetylsalicylic acid, betaxolol, sotalol, bezafibrate, gemfibrozil, bezafibrate, cimetidine and ranitidine displayed LC_{50} values higher than 100 mg/L, which, according to EU-Directive 93/67/EEC, are classified as not being harmful for aquatic organisms⁹².

(a.5) *Neuroactive compounds (antiepileptics, antidepressants)* :

The serotonin re-uptake inhibitor fluoxetine is apparently the most acute toxic human pharmaceutical reported

so far with acute toxicity ranging from EC_{50} (48 h, alga) = 0.024 mg/L to LC_{50} (48 h) = 2 mg/L⁹³. Diazepam and carbamazepine, both antiepileptics, can be classified as potentially harmful to aquatic organisms, because most of the acute toxicity data are below 100 mg/L.

(b) *Chronic effects* :

Many aquatic species are continuously exposed over long periods of time or even over their entire life cycle. Evaluation of the chronic potential of micropollutants, e.g. pharmaceuticals, is therefore important. However, there is a lack of chronic data, and where available, chronic toxicity is marginally known.

(b.1) *Beta-blockers* :

As fish contains β_2 -receptors in heart and liver and probably in reproductive tissues⁹⁴, unspecific antagonists such as propranolol may be active in fish. In fact, propranolol indicated chronic toxicity not only on the cardiovascular system, but also on reproduction. The no-observed-effect-concentration (NOEC) and lowest-observed-effect-concentration (LOEC) of propranolol affecting reproduction in *C. dubia* were 125 and 250 μ g/L, and reproduction was affected after 27 days of exposure in *H. azteca* at 100 μ g/L⁸⁹.

(b.2) *Analgesics and non-steroidal antiinflammatory drugs* :

NSAIDs inhibit the synthesis and release of prostaglandins via COX inhibition and these compounds are the most consumed category of drugs. Acetylsalicylic acid affected reproduction in *D. magna* and *D. longispina* at concentrations of 1.8 mg/L⁹⁵. Diclofenac is commonly found in wastewater at median concentration of 0.81 μ g/L whereas the maximal concentration in wastewater and surface water is up to 2 μ g/L⁹⁵.

(b.3) *Blood lipid lowering agents* :

Data on this class of compounds are rare. Fibrates have been evaluated by traditional toxicity tests. The following NOEC were found for clofibric acid in *C. dubia* [NOEC (7 days) = 640 μ g/L], the rotifer *B. calyciflorus* [NOEC (2 days) = 246 μ g/L], and in early life stages of zebrafish [NOEC (10 days) = 70 mg/L]⁹⁶. Gemfibrozil occurred in blood plasma of goldfish after exposure over 14 days at 113 times higher levels than in water (bioconcentration factor of 113)⁹⁶.

(b.4) Neuroactive compounds :

Among neuroactive compounds, most data were reported for the antiepileptic carbamazepine and selective serotonin re-uptake inhibitors (SSRI); other neuroactive compounds were very rarely or not evaluated. Traditional toxicity tests showed chronic toxicity of carbamazepine in *C. dubia* [NOEC (7 days) = 25 µg/L], in the rotifer *B. calyciflorus* [NOEC (2 days) = 377 µg/L], and in early life stages of zebrafish [NOEC (10 days) = 25 mg/L]⁹⁶.

(b.5) Steroid hormones :

Steroid hormones are a class of organic compounds which are used in both human and veterinary medicines. It includes sex hormones to control and treat sexual function and disorder. Corticosteroids are used to treat allergic and inflammatory disorders. Parasites and their hosts mutually influence various physiological aspects of the other's functional biology with the help of hormones⁹⁷. Interactions between host endocrine and immune systems influence the susceptibility to disease and parasite success is frequently enhanced in endocrine modified hosts. Host hormone levels may also directly or indirectly affect the physiology, behaviour and development of parasites⁹⁷. Due to widespread use of human steroid contraceptives and their occurrence in the aquatic environment, steroid hormones emerged as most serious aquatic environment toxicants. They have been associated with endocrine disruptive conditions in fish and aquatic organisms⁹⁸.

(b.6) Antiparasitic compounds :

The disturbance to the aquatic ecosystem is caused by different antiparasitic compounds. Ivermectin has a number of implications for host-parasite relationships. Invertebrates are hosts to a range of parasites with zooplankton acting as important intermediate hosts for many helminth parasites of fish. As a result, they may create complications for fish in aquatic system⁹⁹.

(b.7) Neuroactive compounds :

A large range of drugs are available which interact with the central nervous system and most are a risk to aquatic environments. They include antiepileptic drugs, which decrease overall neuronal activity; antidepressants, which inhibit the re-uptake of serotonin; antipsychotics, which bind to dopamine receptors; anxiolytic, which bind to benzodiazepine receptors; stimulants, which bind to adenosine receptors; and cholinergic agonists, which bind

to nicotinic-Ach receptors¹⁰⁰.

4.2.2. Human toxicity due to consumed pharmaceuticals

Pharmaceuticals do not always reveal all possible effects, side-effects or adverse reactions during the pre-marketing investigation, preclinical and clinical trials of a new medicinal product. Pharmaceuticals have the potential to cause adverse effects. An adverse effect, be it an adverse drug reaction (ADR) or an adverse drug event (ADE), is an unexpected, unwanted, unpleasant, noxious, or harmful consequence associated with the use of a medication with a standard therapeutic dose by the proper route of administration, for the purpose of prophylaxis, diagnosis, or treatment of disease condition. This explanation does not include the effects resulting from medication abuse, addiction, overdose or withdrawal, or error of administration. Postmarketing experience published in the literature has shown that most ADRs are either related to the dose or drug interaction. Therefore, ADRs are a major problem in drug therapy. Drug-induced adverse reactions are the leading cause of morbidity and mortality in healthcare and they should therefore be considered in the differential diagnosis of a wide variety of medical disorders¹⁰¹.

Post marketing survey revealed many adverse reactions which are reported during medical treatment of a large number of patients with prescribed medicinal products¹⁰². This may be due to failure to mimic the factors or co-factors of real life during clinical trial. The introduction of a new pharmaceutical as a potential drug into the medical market place, therefore, always carries unknown risks, as numerous instances like thalidomide disaster in 1961 during the past decades have demonstrated. In this situation, the alertness of the prescribing physician, other medical staff and the quality of the operational system for reporting adverse reactions are crucial. The thalidomide disaster in 1961 stimulated national and international actions towards assuring the safety of drugs and reducing the risk of drug adverse reactions. The successful effort of the World Health Assembly was that the pharmaceutical industry overcame its mistrust of drug regulatory authorities, becoming with them, and with experts in university medical faculties and international medical societies, an essential and valued partner in the pursuit of drug safety. A way had to be found of associ-

ating the pharmaceutical industry with the World Health Organization (WHO), and it was that the Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences (CIOMS), as a nongovernmental organization with a mandate to cooperate with WHO, was in a position to play a particular role. Under its auspices, the pharmaceutical industry could cooperate with regulatory authorities, registered medical experts and WHO in projects for promoting drug safety^{103,104}. From the view point of adverse drug reactions (ADRs), toxicology has two main goals – (i) to identify and characterize the potential for harmful effects that can be produced in biological systems, particularly laboratory animals, by a drug, and to suggest therapeutic circumstances in which toxic responses may occur and/or are unlikely to occur and (ii) to detect unexpected adverse clinical reactions, i.e. those not predicted by conventional animal and clinical studies, and to investigate the mechanism in additional toxicological studies, often of nonstandard design, in order to understand these reactions and possibly how to avoid or ameliorate them.

Different factors such as patient-related factors (age, sex, disease, genetics, geography), drug-related factors (type of drug, route of administration – intramuscular, intravenous and topical administrations are more likely to cause hypersensitivity reactions; oral medications are less likely to result in drug hypersensitivity – duration of therapy, dosage, and bioavailability), interactions with other drugs influence the incidence and severity of ADRs³⁰. ADRs may be classified as follows¹⁰⁵:

(1) Type A (augmented) – Reactions which are predictable from the known pharmacology often representing an exaggeration of the pharmacological effect of the drug.

(2) Type B (idiosyncratic) – Reactions which are not predictable from knowledge of the basic pharmacology of the drug often exhibiting marked inter-individual susceptibility.

(3) Type C (chemical) – Reactions whose biological characteristics can either be predicted or rationalised in terms of chemical structure.

Here, we mention those drug-induced toxicity and adverse effects which are largely emerged as the main challenge in drug discovery to make more efficacious and less toxic drugs and which are tested in pre-clinical and clinical trials.

4.2.2.1. Arthritic and connective tissue disorders

Among the more interesting and important adverse consequences of drug therapy are a range of joint and connective tissue complaints that may mimic or reproduce primary rheumatologic diseases. In 1972 Bailey noted an association between quinolone antibiotics and a rheumatic syndrome¹⁰⁶. Van der Linden and co-workers compared patients receiving fluoroquinolones to patients receiving other antibiotics. Among 1841 fluoroquinolone users and 9406 users of other antibiotics, 22 met criteria for tendinitis¹⁰⁷. Williams and co-workers investigated the effect of ciprofloxacin on canine tendon fibroblasts¹⁰⁸. They incubated Achilles tendons, paratendons, and shoulder capsules with three concentrations of ciprofloxacin and demonstrated a reduction in fibroblast proliferation (66–68%), collagen synthesis (36–48%), and proteoglycan synthesis (14–60%). Minocycline-induced autoimmune hepatitis may occur as an isolated entity or as a part of the aforementioned syndrome (98). Antituberculosis (anti-TB) drugs have been reported to induce rheumatic syndromes, including lupus-like disease and gout¹⁰⁹.

4.2.2.2. Immunotoxicity

Immunotoxicity can be induced in various ways. Direct immunotoxicity is expressed as immunosuppression or immunostimulation. On the other hand, indirect immunotoxicity is mainly expressed as immunohypersensitivity or autoimmunity. The indirect immunotoxicity is caused by immune responses to the chemical or to self-determinants altered by the chemical¹¹⁰.

The regulatory guidance on the testing of the immunotoxicity of pharmaceuticals has been explicitly integrated into the Note for Guidance on Repeated Dose Toxicity¹¹¹. This European guidance document came into force in October 2000. After that other regulatory authority, such as the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and the Japanese Ministry of Health, Labour, and Welfare (MHLW), followed. A draft FDA document on immunotoxicity was published in 2001 and was finalized in October 2002¹¹². FDA chose total different aspects of immunotoxicity such as immunosuppression, autoimmunity, and allergy.

4.2.2.3. Cardiovascular toxicity

Cardiotoxicity is one of the most common types of

serious, life-threatening adverse effects (AEs) for drugs and medical products reported in FDA CDER's MedWatch program (<http://www.fda.gov/medwatch/>). Among the three organ systems, ICSAS investigated that cardiac and cardiovascular AEs are more common than AEs of the hepatobiliary or the urinary tract systems in MedWatch in FDA's post-market surveillance databases. Again, a study of all safety withdrawals of prescription drugs from worldwide markets from 1960 to 1999¹¹³ reported that, internationally, the heart is one of the most common organs which are affected by toxicities leading to drug withdrawal. Therefore, cardiotoxicity represents as a main concern for both regulatory safety estimation and high responsibility for pharmaceutical industry product revenue. Some examples of drugs that have been removed from the market due to cardiac AEs include : astemizole, chlorphentermine, cisapride, cloforex, dexfenfluramine and terfenadine¹¹³. These drugs are capable of producing serious/life-threatening cardiovascular effects, including sudden cardiac death, acute cardiac beriberi, cardiac arrhythmias, and ischemic complications related to severe and prolonged vasoconstriction¹¹⁴. In most of the cases, drug-induced arrhythmias can be attributed to QT prolongation (drug-induced long QT syndrome) which can further be identified to interaction with a particular cardiac ion channel known as human Ether-a-go-go Related Gene (hERG) (Aronov and Goldman, 2004). The post-marketing scenario shows that arrhythmias is a major reason for 25% of drug withdrawals¹¹⁵.

4.2.2.4. Pulmonary toxicity

Pulmonary toxicity is an important type of drug-induced toxicity. For example, amiodarone (AM) is a highly effective and widely used drug of cardiac dysrhythmias; however, AM therapy is related with severe adverse effects like pulmonary toxicity. The incidence of amiodarone-induced pulmonary toxicity (AIPT) has been variously reported to range from 5% to 25% in patients who are receiving AM doses of 400 mg/day or higher. In some cases pulmonary fibrosis is also developed. AM also potentially causes acute lung damage¹¹⁶.

4.2.2.5. Carcinogenicity and genotoxicity

Major drug-induced toxicities are genotoxicity and carcinogenicity. The regulatory authorities of Europe,

Japan and USA recommend that genotoxicity and carcinogenicity studies are performed before application for marketing approval of pharmaceuticals to assess the potential risk of genotoxic and carcinogenic effects to humans. Unambiguously, genotoxic compounds are supposed to be carcinogens and do not need to be subjected to long-term carcinogenicity studies¹¹⁷. The International Agency for Research on Cancer¹¹⁸ in the 91 volumes of IARC Monographs on the Evaluation of Carcinogenic Risks to Humans published in the years from 1972 to 2007 examined more than 200 drugs. It included only 7 analgesics and anti-inflammatory drugs : analgesics containing phenacetin, classified as carcinogenic to humans (Group 1); phenazopyridine, classified as possibly carcinogenic to humans (Group 2B); oxyphenbutazone, paracetamol, and phenylbutazone, considered non-classifiable as to their carcinogenicity in humans (Group 3).

4.2.2.6. Hepatotoxicity

The liver is one of the most important organs in drug toxicity for two reasons. First of all, it is functionally interposed between the site of absorption and the systemic circulation and second, it is a major site of metabolism and elimination of xenobiotics. These features make it a preferred target organ for drug toxicity. Drug-induced liver injury (DILI) therefore poses a major clinical problem. DILI has become the leading cause of acute liver failure and transplantation in Western countries in recent time^{119,120}. From a recent report¹²¹ it is clear that intrinsic hepatotoxicity following acetaminophen overdose accounts for the majority of cases of drug-induced acute liver failure in the United States and the United Kingdom. However, more than 1000 drugs and herbal products have been related with idiosyncratic hepatotoxicity¹²¹. Idiosyncratic hepatotoxicity is responsible for more than 10% of all cases of acute liver failure. DILI also represents a major challenge for industry and regulatory authorities because it is a leading cause for cessation of further drug development in preclinical and clinical phases. Again, it is also the most common single adverse drug reaction leading to rejection of market approval^{119,120}. In Table 6 we categorised different drugs involved in different hepatotoxicity¹²².

Table 6. Representative list of different drugs involved in different types of hepatotoxicity

Different types of hepatotoxicity	Pattern	Involved drugs
Acute liver failure	Necrosis with inflammation	Isoniazid, monoamine oxidase inhibitors, anticonvulsants (phenytoin, valproate), antimicrobials (sulfonamides, cotrimoxazole, ketoconazole)
	Necrosis with no inflammation	Acetaminophen, cocaine, carbon tetrachloride
	Microvesicular steatosis with little or no inflammation	Tetracycline, nucleoside analogues
Chronic hepatitis	Autoimmune marker-negative	Lisinopril, sulfonamides, trazodone, uracil, tegafur, tamoxifen, methotrexate
	Drug-induced autoimmune hepatitis	Minocycline, nitrofurantoin, methyl dopa, clometacin
Cholestasis	Bland cholestasis	Anabolic/androgenic steroids, oestrogenic steroids, NSAIDs (nimesulide, piroxicam)
	Cholestatic hepatitis	Chlorpromazine, clarithromycin
Granulomatous hepatitis I	-	Isoniazid, interferon, phenytoin, allopurinol
Steatosis/steatohepatitis	Macrovesicular steatosis	Alcohol, steroids, total parenteral nutrition, gold, chlorinated hydrocarbons, chemotherapeutic agents (5-fluorouracil)
	Microvesicular steatosis	Cocaine, tetracycline, valproic acid, zidovudine
	Steatohepatitis	Amiodarone, chemotherapeutic agents (irinotecan), perhexiline

4.2.2.7. Olfactory mucosal toxicity

The olfactory mucosa (OM) is an important target for metabolism-dependent toxicity of drugs. OM has a high capability to metabolize inhaled and blood-borne drugs. The Bowman's glands in the lamina propria express high levels of various cytochrome P450 (CYP). As a result it is a sensitive target for certain CYP-activated toxicants. Therefore, drug induces toxicity in the OM is due to covalent binding in the Bowman's glands¹²³.

4.2.2.8. Nephrotoxicity

Nephrotoxicity is another major reason that drugs are withdrawn after marketing. Therefore, it is major concern to both the FDA and pharmaceutical companies. The number of cases of serious adverse effects (SAEs) in marketed drugs has climbed fast¹²⁴. The US FDA and European Medicines Agency (EMA) recently approved a set of seven urinary proteins as biomarkers of nephrotoxicity. The reports were submitted by the predictive safety testing consortium (PSTC) in collaboration with multiple pharmaceutical companies to the voluntary exploratory data submission (VXDS) committee of the FDA. The FDA and EMA declared that these biomarkers are

for regulatory use in certain preclinical studies (www.c-path.org/pdf/PSTC_nephro_VXDS_summay_final.pdf).

5. Endpoints

For the development of QSAR models, toxicity of a compound should be estimated on specific biological endpoints. With literature search we have found the most commonly used ecotoxicological endpoints by the research community. In Table 7 we assemble almost every possible endpoints which are used hugely by scientists.

6. Quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR)

QSAR attempts to correlate structural/molecular properties (descriptors) with biological activities, for a set of similar compounds by means of statistical methods. As a result, a simple mathematical relationship is established:

Biological activity = f (chemical structure or property)

Applications of QSAR can be extended to any molecular design purpose, prediction of different kinds of biological activities, lead compound optimization, classification, diagnosis and elucidation of mechanisms of drug action, toxicity prediction of environmental toxicants (pol-

Table 7. Representative list of ecotoxicological and human toxicity test batteries (endpoints)

Types	Name/Species	Description and characteristics	Notes	Refs.
Fish	Zebrafish (<i>Danio rerio</i>)	It plays an important role in ecotoxicology as a prominent vertebrate. Acute toxicity test of chemicals are done by <i>Danio rerio</i>	One of the most commonly applied model animal tests in regulatory ecotoxicology to this day is the fish acute lethality test. It is standardized under the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development and is used to test chemicals as well as industrial effluents	(http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/danio)
Protozoa	<i>Tetrahymena thermophila</i> , <i>Tetrahymena pyriformis</i>	Free-living unicellular ciliated protozoa that can also switch from commensalistic to pathogenic modes of survival. They are common in fresh-water	An attractive candidate for the assessment of the environmental impact of toxicants. In addition to the environmental safety, toxicity to this organism has proven useful in estimating the toxic potencies of chemicals	(http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tetrahymena)
Crustaceans	<i>Daphnia magna</i> , <i>Daphnia pulex</i> , <i>Daphnia ambigua</i> , <i>Daphnia melanica</i>	Small, planktonic crustaceans, between 0.2 and 5 mm in length. <i>Daphnia</i> are members of the order Cladocera, and are one of the several small aquatic crustaceans commonly called water fleas. They live in various aquatic environments ranging from acidic swamps to freshwater lakes, ponds, streams and rivers	An important freshwater invertebrate species in aquatic food webs has been used world-wide for many years as a representative test species for ecotoxicological evaluation of industrial chemicals. Immobilization test was done by <i>Daphnia</i>	(http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Daphnia)
	<i>Thamnocephalus platyurus</i>	Small Crustaceans	Used as a biological species for ecological toxicity testing of chemicals (mainly oxides)	(http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Thamnocephalus)
Bacterium	<i>Vibrio fischeri</i>	A gram-negative rod-shaped bacterium found globally in marine environments. It has bioluminescent properties and found predominantly in symbiosis with various marine animals, such as the bobtail squid. It is heterotrophic and moves by means of flagella. Free living <i>V. fischeri</i> survives on decaying organic matter	Key research organism for examination of microbial bioluminescence, quorum sensing, and bacterial-animal symbiosis. It is formerly known as <i>Photobacterium phosphoreum</i> , is of technical interest according to Spanish regulations. Spanish Order 13 October 1989 was adopted to identify property H-14 (ecotoxicity) of hazardous wastes. Ecotoxicity of a chemical was done by luminescence inhibition of <i>Vibrio fischeri</i>	(http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Vibrio_fischeri)
Yeast	<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	It is a species of budding yeast and one of the most intensively	Ecotoxicologically important species for toxicity prediction	(http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Saccharomyces_cerevisiae)

		studied eukaryotic model organisms in molecular and cell biology. Small in size, accessible, reproduction time quick and potentially economic		
Algae	<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i> , <i>Chlorella pyrenoidosa</i>	Chlorella is a genus of unicellular green algae which comprises a major component of the phytoplankton. It is a popular food supplement in Japan and is marketed as a nutritional supplement in the United States	Studying the toxic action of organic compounds to <i>C. vulgaris</i> has become an important subject for humanity	(http://www.pdrhealth.com/drug_info/nmdrugprofiles/nutsupdrugs/chl_0068.shtml)
	<i>Pseudokirchneriella subcapitata</i> (formerly known as <i>Selenastrum capricornutum</i>)	Primary producers of the aquatic ecosystem, occupy an important position in the aquatic food chain. Due to wide spread distribution, ideal test organisms for toxicological studies	Ecotoxicity is studied by growth rate inhibition of green algae <i>P. subcapitata</i>	(ISO/TC 147/SC 5/WG N 182, 1999)
	<i>Scenedesmus obliquus</i>	Unicellular and cells were grown heterotrophically in the dark	Used for toxicity prediction	(http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Scenedesmus)
Tadpoles	<i>Bufo vulgaris formosus</i> , <i>Rana japonica</i> (Japanese brown frog)	Tadpoles, a common and sensitive species, the larva of the frogs. Frogs are typical amphibious animals bridging the gap between aquatic and terrestrial animals. The larvae of frogs, tadpoles, proved to be more sensitive to some pesticides than adults	Amphibians are often the main vertebrate group at risk of exposure to contaminants in ephemeral systems. Regularly used for toxicity testing purposes and risk assessments, for their sensitivity to the endpoint of the ecotoxicity have been widely employed, and recommended by the EU-TGD	

lutant chemicals, gas etc.) and prediction of drug-induced toxicity¹²⁵. The objective of structure-activity modelling is to analyze and detect the determining factors for the measured activity for a particular system, in order to have an insight of the mechanism and behaviour of the studied system. For such a purpose, the employed strategy is to generate a mathematical model that connects experimental measures with a set of chemical descriptors determined from the molecular structure for a set of compounds. The derived model should have as good predictive capabilities as possible to predict the studied biological or physicochemical behaviour for new compounds.

The factors governing the events in a biological system are represented by a multitude of physicochemical descriptors, which can include parameters to account for hydrophobicity, electronic properties, steric effects, and topology, among others. These descriptors were determined empirically in the past but, more recently, they can be calculated by using computational methods^{126,127}.

QSAR started with simple correlations between chemical structure and biological activity by Hansch in the 1960s¹²⁸.

$$\log 1/C = a_0 + a_1x_1 + a_2x_2 + \dots + a_nx_n$$
 where *C* is the molar concentration of the compound to

produce a defined biological response, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are descriptors and $a_0, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n$ are regression coefficients. The knowledge of the biological system, various factors regulating physiological processes and those contributing to pathological states, a thorough examination of molecular structures of drugs/chemicals and their properties and unearthing of the factors modulating biological activity (toxicity) of drugs/chemicals are required to find out the biochemical rationale of drug action or toxicity prediction of drugs or chemicals. Such understanding helps to develop more effective drugs and less toxic chemicals in a scientific way potentially reducing the cost of drug discovery, time, and manpower¹²⁹. The process of QSAR model development can be generally mainly divided into four stages : (i) data preparation, (ii) data analysis, (iii) model validation and (iv) data interpretation. A large set of new and traditional descriptors are used to create improved QSAR models that characterize and predict important biological responses. The QSAR models are developed using a variety of chemometric tools^{130,131} such as stepwise multiple linear regression (MLR), partial least squares (PLS), genetic function approximation (GFA), genetic partial least squares (GPLS) and so on. The statistical quality of the models developed can be examined by different statistical parameters¹³² such as determination coefficient (R^2), explained variance (R^2_a), standard error of estimate (s) and variance ratio (F) at specified degrees of freedom (df). Again, the validation strategies are very crucial to check the reliability of the developed models for their possible application on a new set of data, and confidence of prediction can thus be judged¹³³. For many researchers, validation of a model is little more than an assessment of statistical fit and, occasionally, predictivity using cross-validation techniques. Yet, it is now being well accepted that validation is a more rational process that includes assessment of issues such as data quality, applicability of the model and mechanistic interpretability in addition to statistical assessment¹³⁴. For validation of QSAR models, usually four strategies are adopted¹³⁵ : (i) internal validation or cross-validation (leave-one-out or leave-many-out technique); (ii) validation by dividing the data set into training and test compounds; (iii) true external validation by application of model on external data; and (iv) data randomization or Y-scrambling. Robustness and predictivity are checked by differ-

ent validation parameters such as predicted residual sum of squares (PRESS), cross-validated R^2 (Q^2), predictive R^2 (R^2_{pred}), modified r^2 [$r_m^2(LOO)$ and $r_m^2(test)$] and overall model predictivity [$r_m^2(overall)$] (all bearing a threshold value of 0.5)^{131,136,137}. The steps for development of a QSAR model are shown in Fig. 1.

The applicability domain (AD) is an important aspect in QSAR model validation¹³⁸. AD is a theoretical region in chemical space, defined by the model descriptors and modelled response. It indicates that only those compounds that fall within this domain of applicability can be considered reliable for prediction¹³⁸. 'Extent of extrapolation'¹³⁹ is a method of defining applicability domain which is calculated on the basis of the leverage (h_i) value for each chemical or drug used for the QSAR model development. Regularly used QSAR studies are mostly two-dimensional 2D (performed using different physicochemical and topological parameters) and three-dimensional 3D (performed using various 3D descriptors)¹⁴⁰. In recent time, four-dimensional 4D (where conformational and alignment freedom are incorporated in model development)¹⁴¹, five-dimensional 5D (which considers different induced fit protocols) (<http://www.dddmag.com/qsar-prediction-beyond-the-fourth.aspx>) and six-dimensional 6D (which allows simultaneous consideration of different solvation models) (http://www.modelling.unibas.ch/UB_BB2.html) QSAR models are also being used by different groups of researchers. With the progress of molecular modelling and X-ray crystallography, QSAR has a large impact in drug design and development. In terms of ligand design, it has an important role with other approaches such as structure-based ligand design and other rational drug design approaches including docking methods in recent time. QSAR methods are now urgently needed for predicting toxicity of chemicals for regulatory decisions and screening of drug-induced toxicity of new drug entity. In recent years, lots of *in silico* models have been applied to predict drug-induced toxicity and chemical toxicity to the environment and human. The present review provides a survey of the various QSAR models reported mostly in the last 20 years by different groups of authors on toxicity prediction of chemicals and drugs to the environment, human and living animals. However, considering the broadness of the area covered, this report may not be exhaustive.

Fig. 1. Flowchart for development of a quantitative structure-activity relationship model.

7. Databases

A large number of chemical toxicity information databases are publicly available and the number is increasing day by day. As a result, public sources of toxicity data are the first to be tapped into for computational modeling and *in silico* toxicology software programs. Still these databases are very small compared to drug discovery compound libraries in the industry. Recent initiatives requir-

ing greater use of *in silico* technologies have called for transparency and development of toxicity database information that is available to the public at no cost. Table 8 summarizes the many publicly available toxicity databases and electronic resources describing human health effects of chemicals useful in risk assessment, safety evaluation, and hazard characterization. Therefore, the research community should take initiatives to develop more databases for public and administration uses.

Table 8. Representative list of publicly available databases containing information on the environmental and human toxicity and QSAR

Types of toxicity	Sl. no.	Databases	Website	Description and notes	
Drug, Biological products, Food and Agrochemical induced toxicity	1.	AERS	http://www.fda.gov/Drugs/GuidanceComplianceRegulatoryInformation/Surveillance/AdverseDrugEffects/default.htm	US FDA/CDER Adverse Effects Reporting system of post-market safety surveillance for all approved drug and therapeutic biologic products	
	2.	CEDI/ADI Database	http://www.fda.gov/Food/FoodIngredientsPackaging/FoodContactSubstancesFCS/CEDIADIDatabase/default.htm	US FDA/CFSAN Cumulative Estimated Daily Intake/Acceptable Daily Intake Database of food contact substances	
	3.	CERES	http://www.fda.gov/food	Chemical Evaluation and Risk Estimation System (CERES). US FDA/CFSAN Food. Databases on toxicity of food, drugs, agro. and industrial chemicals, structural alerts, and QSAR-based toxicity predictions	
	4.	DITOP	http://bioinf.xmu.edu.cn/databases/ADR/index.html	Drug-induced Toxicity-Related Protein Database provides DITRPs-related information. Related toxicities include overdose toxicity, idiosyncratic toxicity, drug-drug interactions and genetic toxicity	
	5.	Drugs@FDA	http://www.fda.gov/Drugs/InformationOnDrugs/ucm135821.htm	US FDA-approved drug products	
	6.	EAFUS	http://www.fda.gov/Food/FoodIngredientsPackaging/ucm115326.htm	US FDA/CFSAN Contains ingredients directly added to food in conduction with the Priority Based-Assessment of Food Additive Database	
	7.	FDA Poisonous Plant Database	http://www.accessdata.fda.gov/scripts/plantox/index.cfm	US FDA/CFSAN database with references to scientific literature describing toxic properties of plants	
	8.	MRTD	http://www.fda.gov/AboutFDA/CentersOffices/CDER/ucm092199.htm	US FDA/CDER/OPS/SRS/ICSAS Database on the max. recommended therapeutic dose of 1220 pharmaceuticals	
	Industrial chemicals induced toxicity to human and environment	9.	ACToR	http://actor.epa.gov/actor/faces/ACToRHome.jsp	US EPA National Center for Computational Toxicology. Data on high and medium production volume industrial chemicals. The database is searchable including chemical structure, physicochemical values, and provides <i>in vitro</i> and <i>in vivo</i> toxicology data
		10.	CEBS	http://cebs.niehs.nih.gov/cebs-browser/cebsHome.do;jsessionid=E604E0061D6B156B29F9525F1B86BEA8	US NIH/NIEHS Chemical Effects in Biological Systems Knowledgebase; integrates genomic and biological data including dose-response studies in toxicology and pathology
		11.	Danish (Q)SAR Database	http://ecbqsar.jrc.ec.europa.eu/	Danish EPA repository of estimates from over 70 QSAR models and health effects for 166072 chemicals

Table-8 (contd.)

12.	DSSTox	http://www.epa.gov/ncct/dsstox/index.html	Distributed Structure-Searchable Toxicity Database Network of downloadable, standardized chemical structure files associated with toxicity data
13.	HERA	http://www.heraproject.com/RiskAssessment.cfm	Human and Environmental Risk Assessment on Ingredients and Household Cleaning Products: supplied and formulated by European manufacturers
14.	Household Products Database	http://hpd.nlm.nih.gov/	US Department of Health and Human Services database with MSDSs of household products with health effects ratings and produce chemical information
15.	IRIS	http://cfpub.epa.gov/ncea/iris/index.cfm	Integrated Risk Information System; a compilation of electronic reports on environmental substances and their potential to cause human health effects
16.	ITER	http://www.tera.org/iter/	Database of human health risk values and cancer classifications for over 600 environmental chemicals
17.	JECDB	http://dra4.nihs.go.jp/mhlw_data/jsp/SearchPageENG.jsp	Japanese Ministry of Health, Labour and Welfare Chemical Toxicity Database of environmental chemicals
18.	JRC QSAR Database	http://ecb.jrc.ec.europa.eu/qsar/background/	European Commission, Joint Research Centre's Database of REACH relevant QSARs
19.	MRL	http://www.atsdr.cdc.gov/mrls/index.html	US DHHS/ATSDR minimal risk levels for hazardous substances
20.	NTP	http://ntp.niehs.nih.gov/	US NIH/NIEHS National Toxicology Program testing status and information of agents registered in the US of public health interest
21.	RAIS	http://rais.ornl.gov/tox/tox_values.shtml	The Risk Assessment Information System of chemical-specific toxicity values
22.	SCOGS	http://www.fda.gov/Food/FoodIngredientsPackaging/GenerallyRecognizedasSafeGRAS/GRASSubstancesSCOGSDatabase/default.htm	US FDA/CFSAN database resource on toxicology and safety reports made by the Select Committee on GRAS Substances
23.	STITCH	http://stitch.embl.de/	Search Tool for Interactions of Chemicals (STITCH). Knowledge database to explore known and predicted interactions between proteins and small-molecule chemicals for understanding of molecular and cellular functions. Over 68000 chemicals are represented
24.	TAP	URL not available	Toxicological Activity Profile database of acute, subchronic, and chronic data from the US EPA Office of Air Quality Planning and Standards
25.	Toxtree	http://ecb.jrc.ec.europa.eu/qsar/qsar-tools/index.php?c=TOXTREE	An open-source application of Joint Research Centre (EC) that places chemicals into categories

			and predicts various kinds of toxic effects by applying decision tree approaches
	26.	Toxmatch	http://ecb.jrc.ec.europa.eu/qsar/qsar-tools/index.php?c=TOXMATCH
			An open-source computer program of Joint Research Centre (EC) that encodes several chemical similarity indices in order to facilitate the grouping of chemicals, thereby supporting the development of chemicals categories and the application of read-across between analogues
	27.	DART	http://ecb.jrc.ec.europa.eu/qsar/qsar-tools/index.php?c=DART
			An open-source computer program of Joint Research Centre (EC) to implement a variety of ranking methods
Carcinogenesis and Genotoxicity	28.	Cal/EPA	http://www.oehha.ca.gov/risk/ChemicalDB/index.asp
			State of California EPA Toxicity Criteria Database of chronic reference exposure levels and cancer potency information
	29.	CCRIS	http://toxnet.nlm.nih.gov/cgi-bin/sis/htmlgen?CCRIS
			Chemical carcinogenesis research information system
	30.	CPDB	http://potency.berkeley.edu/
			University of California, Berkeley, carcinogenic potency database
	31.	GAC	http://www.niehs.nih.gov/research/resources/databases/gac/index.cfm
			US NIH/NIEHS Genetic Alterations in Cancer database; quantifies specific mutations found in cancers induced by environmental chemicals
	32.	GAP	Software
	33.	Gene-Tox	http://toxnet.nlm.nih.gov/cgi-bin/sis/htmlgen?GENETOX
			US NLM Peer-reviewed genetic toxicology test data for over 3000 chemicals
	34.	IARC Monograph	http://monographs.iarc.fr/
			International Agency for Research on Cancer Monographs on the evaluation of carcinogenic risks to humans
	35.	ISSCAN	http://www.iss.it/ampp/dati/cont.php?id=233&lang=1&tipo=7
			Istituto Superiore di Sanità, Italy, database on chemical carcinogens. Information on chemical tested with the long-term carcinogenicity bioassay on rodents
	36.	LAZAR	http://www.in-silico.de/
			Lazy Structure-Activity Relationships Database: QSAR predictions for liver toxicity, mutagenicity, and carcinogenicity
	37.	Oncology Tools	http://www.fda.gov/CDER/cancer/oncrefto.htm
			US FDA/CDER database on approved cancer drugs with approved indications; includes common toxicity criteria
	38.	RITA	http://www.item.fraunhofer.de/reni/public/rita/index.php
			Registry of Industrial Toxicology Animal-data: comparing and interpreting rodent carcinogenicity studies and tumour data

Table-8 (contd.)

Developmental toxicity	39.	BDSM	http://systemsanalysis.louisville.edu/	Developmental toxicity database and open-source software for discovery of developmental toxicants from the University of Louisville
	40.	DevTox	http://www.devtox.org/	Developmental toxicity database for various strains of common laboratory animals developed by German industry and government
Aquatic toxicity	41.	ECOTOX	http://cfpub.epa.gov/ecotox/	Information on adverse effects of single chemical stressors to ecologically relevant aquatic and terrestrial species. ECOTOX includes more than 400000 test records covering 5900 aquatic and terrestrial species and 8400 chemicals
	42.	ESIS	http://ecb.jrc.it/esis/ and http://ecb.jrc.ec.europa.eu/esis/	Provides access to chemicals from several European regulatory inventories and to the data, associated with them. The search is by number (CAS or EC), chemical name and molecular formula. It allows access to IUCLID data sheets, if available. For HPV chemicals, IUCLID stores more than 38000 acute (including microbial toxicity) and about 3000 chronic toxicity data
	43.	TEXTRATOX	http://www.vet.utk.edu/TETRATOX/index.php	The University of Tennessee Institute of Agriculture. A collection of aquatic toxic potency data for more than 2400 industrial organic compounds
	44.	TOXNET	http://www.nlm.nih.gov/pubs/factsheets/toxnetfs.html	The database contains toxicological information for chemicals but also includes information on exposure, industrial hygiene, emergency handling procedures, environmental fate, etc. TOXNET is a cluster of databases, which have separate searching facilities
	45.	USGS	http://137.227.231.90/data/acute/acute.html	Aquatic acute toxicity tests conducted by the US Geological Survey, Columbia Environmental Research Center
	46.	OECD HPV database	http://cs3-hq.oecd.org/scripts/hpv/	Stores at least minimum set of data (including acute aquatic toxicity), necessary to determine a potential hazard. Data are available through existing reports. Searchable by chemical name, CAS, sponsoring country and stage
	47.	N-Class database, Kemi	http://apps.kemi.se/nclass/	Based on substance environmental hazard data (available), the N-Class database calculates aquatic classifications of preparations both according to Directive 1999/45/EEC and to the Globally Harmonized System (GHS). Data available through summary records for a substance
	48.	Riskline, Kemi	http://apps.kemi.se/riskline/	Contains information on both environment and health Useful for classification and labelling. Provides links to references, associated with a chemical

Pesticides induced toxicity	49.	EXTOXNET	http://extoxnet.orst.edu/ghindex.html	University-based database of issues related to pesticide toxicology
	50.	NPIC	http://npic.orst.edu/	National Pesticide Information Center through Oregon State University and US EPA provides science-based information about pesticides including toxicity
	51.	PAN Pesticide	http://www.pesticideinfo.org/	Pesticide Action Network North America; data on 6500 pesticides, insecticides and herbicides including toxicity, water pollution, ecological toxicity, uses, and regulatory Status
	52.	Pesticide Database	http://chrom.tutms.tut.ac.jp/JINNO/PESDATA/00alphabet.html	Pesticide database at the Toyohashi University of Technology, Japan
	53.	ToxRefDB	http://www.epa.gov/ncct/toxrefdb/	US EPA relational database of standard toxicity test results for pesticides and other environmental chemicals including acute, subchronic, chronic, reproductive, and developmental toxicity in support of the ToxCast program

8. QSAR of chemical and drug-induced toxicity to human and living systems

8.1. QSAR of drug-induced hepatotoxicity

Roy and Ghosh¹⁴² developed QSTR models for acute rat hepatocyte cytotoxicity of a series of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) with Extended Topochemical Atom (ETA) indices. The ETA models were compared with those developed with a pool of other topological indices. They also developed models from the combined pool of topological (ETA and non-ETA) descriptors. The chemometric tools used for model development were multiple linear regression with factor analysis as the variable selection tool, stepwise regression, principal component regression analysis, partial least squares (PLS), genetic function approximation (GFA) and genetic PLS (G/PLS). Use of ETA descriptors along with non-ETA ones increased the statistical quality of the non-ETA models in different techniques except stepwise regression and GFA. The best three models came from GFA, G/PLS and PLS techniques (leave-one-out Q^2 values of 0.871, 0.854 and 0.834, respectively, using combined set of descriptors except for GFA). Use of the ETA parameters in this work suggests that the toxicity increases with bulk and degree of branching. Moreover, heteroatom count and degree of unsaturation are also important for the toxicity.

The molecular mechanism of halobenzene hepatotoxicity was investigated using QSAR study by Chan *et al.*¹⁴³. The usefulness of isolated hepatocytes for predicting *in vivo* xenobiotic toxicity was reassessed by correlating the LC_{50} of 12 halobenzene congeners in phenobarbital (PB)-induced rat hepatocytes *in vitro* determined by accelerated cytotoxicity mechanism screening (ACMS) to the hepatotoxicities reported *in vivo* in PB-induced male Sprague-Dawley (SD) rats. A high correlation ($r^2 = 0.90$) confirmed the application of hepatocytes as a "gold standard" for toxicity testing *in vitro*. QSARs were derived to determine the physico-chemical variables which govern halobenzene toxicity in PB-induced rat and human hepatocytes. The authors found that toxicity in normal rat and normal human hepatocytes both strongly correlate with hydrophobicity ($\log P$), ease of oxidation (E_{HOMO} , energy of the highest occupied molecular orbital) and the asymmetric charge distribution according to arrangement of halogen substituents (dipole moment, μ). This suggests that halobenzene interaction with cytochrome P450 for oxidation is the metabolic activating path for toxicity and is similar in both species. In PB-induced rat hepatocytes, the QSAR derivation is changed, where halobenzene toxicity strongly correlates to $\log P$ and dipole moment, but not E_{HOMO} . QSAR models were developed for bro-

minated and chlorinated methanes using semi-empirical molecular orbital methods by Geissa and Frazier¹⁴⁴. These models can be used to explain the relative potential for given halogenated methane to induce markers of oxidative stress or related damage *in vitro*. The results showed that certain descriptors, such as the molecular orbital energies, bond lengths, and lipophilicity are quantitatively correlated with induction of indicators for oxidative stress and cytotoxicity by halogenated methanes in primary rat hepatocytes. LUMO energy, log *P*, and molar refractivity (MR) are all highly correlated ($R^2 > 0.67$) with each of the response values. The LUMO was negatively correlated, while log *P* and MR are positively correlated. E_{DIFF} displays a small negative correlation ($R^2 > 0.42$) that was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

QSAR models were developed by Matthews *et al.*¹⁴⁵ for predicting rare drug-induced liver and urinary tract injury in humans based upon a database of post-marketing adverse effects (AEs) linked to ≈ 1600 chemical structures. The models were based upon estimated population exposure using AE proportional reporting ratios. Models were constructed for 5 types of liver injury (liver enzyme disorders, cytotoxic injury, cholestasis and jaundice, bile duct disorders, gall bladder disorders) and 6 types of urinary tract injury (acute renal disorders, nephropathies, bladder disorders, kidney function tests, blood in urine, urolithiasis). For model development, 4 QSAR programs (MC4PC, MDL-QSAR, BioEpisteme, and Predictive Data Miner) were used. The best QSAR models exhibited an overall average 92.4% coverage, 86.5% specificity and 39.3% sensitivity. The 4 QSAR programs were demonstrated to be complementary and enhanced performance was obtained by combining predictions from 2 programs (average 78.4% specificity, 56.2% sensitivity). Consensus predictions resulted in better performance as judged by both internal and external validation experiments by the authors.

Roy and Popelier¹⁴⁶ constructed predictive QSAR models for hepatocyte toxicity data of phenols using Quantum Topological Molecular Similarity (QTMS) descriptors along with hydrophobicity (log *P*) as predictor variables. The QTMS descriptors were calculated at different levels of theory including AM1, HF/3-21G(d), HF/6-31G(d), B3LYP/6-31+G(d,p), B3LYP/6-311+G(2d,p) and MP2/6-311+G(2d,p). The external predictability of

the best models at the higher levels of theory is higher than that at the lower levels. The authors showed the advantage of quantum chemically derived descriptors over physicochemical electronic descriptors in QSAR studies.

8.2. QSAR of drug-induced carcinogenicity

Fratev and Benfenati¹⁴⁷ applied a combination of 3D-QSAR, docking, local-binding energy (LBE) and GRID methods to study and predict the mechanism of action of 100 carcinogenic benzene derivatives. Two 3D-QSAR models were obtained: (i) model of mouse carcinogenicity on the basis of 100 chemicals (model 1) and (ii) model of the differences in mouse and rat carcinogenicity on the basis of 73 compounds (model 2). 3D-QSAR maps indicate that in rat there was a higher contribution related to the *ortho* residues, while in mouse the *para* residues were more important, which is in agreement with results from docking analysis. To evaluate the role of P450 metabolic process in carcinogenicity, the following approaches were used by Fratev *et al.* They built 3D models of CYP2E1 for mouse and rat. Docking study was performed and the important ligand-protein residues interactions and oxidation positions of the molecules were identified. Fratev *et al.* calculated the binding energies of the important substituents (local-binding energy - LBE) to quantitatively demonstrate the contribution of the substituents in metabolic processes. Furthermore, a computational procedure was used by them to determine energetically favourable binding sites (GRID examination) of the enzymes. The GRID procedure allowed the identification of some important differences, related to species metabolism in CYP2E1. Comparing GRID, 3D-QSAR maps and LBE results, a similarity was identified, indicating a relationship between P450 metabolic processes and the differences in the carcinogenicity. Fratev *et al.* excellently linked 3D-QSAR, docking, LBE and GRID approaches to study carcinogenicity benzene derivatives chemicals.

Morales *et al.*¹⁴⁸ performed QSAR study of carcinogenicity for several nitro compounds. The authors applied a TOPological substructural molecular design (TOPSMODE) approach for predicting the rodent carcinogenicity of nitrocompounds. The model described 79.10% of the experimental variance, with a standard deviation of 0.424. The predictive power of the model was validated

by leave-one-out validation, with a determination coefficient of 0.666. In addition, this approach enabled the contribution of different fragments to carcinogenic potency to be assessed, thereby making the relationships between structure and carcinogenicity to be transparent. It was identified by Morales *et al.* that the carcinogenic activity of the analysed chemicals was increased by the presence of a primary amine group bonded to the aromatic ring, a manner that was proportional to the ring aromaticity. The nitro group bonded to an aromatic carbon atom is a determinant of carcinogenicity more important than the nitro group bonded to an aliphatic carbon. The TOPS-MODE approach was compared with four other predictive models, but none of these could explain more than 66% of the variance in the carcinogenic potency with the same number of variables.

A QSAR study has been applied by Deeb *et al.*¹⁴⁹ to a data set of 18 sulpha drugs with carcinogenesis activity. Semiempirical quantum chemical calculation (AM1 method) was used to find the optimum 3D geometry of the studied molecules. Two types of molecular descriptors including chemical and electronic ones were used to derive a quantitative relation between the carcinogenesis activity and structural properties. AM1 quantum chemical descriptors such as local charges, E_{HOMO} and E_{LUMO} energies in combination with some physicochemical descriptors were used. The multilinear QSAR equations were obtained by MLR and PLS methods combined with genetic algorithm for variable selection. Among the descriptors used by the different QSAR models, two were related to steric hindrance and molecular bulkiness, some were attributed to HOMO-LUMO energies and the rest were charge-related descriptors. This study indicated that the carcinogenic activity of the studied sulpha drugs is controlled by three major factors : Steric factors had negative effect, which means that more bulky molecules have lower carcinogenicity. The sign of the coefficients of the charge descriptors implies that sulpha drugs with lower carcinogenic activity should have lower negative or higher positive charge on their molecular skeleton. Analysis of the shape of the HOMO orbital of the sulpha drugs indicates that small electron-withdrawing groups at the $-\text{SO}_2\text{-NH-R}$ moiety delocalize the HOMO orbital density on the 4-anilino moiety and hence increase the carcinogenic activity. QSAR modelling was studied by Helguera

*et al.*¹⁵⁰ for predicting the carcinogenic potency of a set of 39 nitroso-compounds. Modelling was performed on spectral moments weighted with Gasteiger-Marsilli atomic charges, polarizability and hydrophobicity, as well as with Abraham indexes, specifically the summation solute hydrogen-bond basicity and the combined dipolarity/polarizability. In this study, the authors explored the possibility of combining Abraham solute descriptors with spectral moments. The QSAR study revealed the importance of the length of the alkyl chains for determining carcinogenic potential of the analysed chemicals, and was able to explain the difference between mono-substituted and di-substituted nitrosoureas as well as to discriminate between isomeric structures with hydroxyl-alkyl and alkyl substituents in different positions. Moreover, this interpretation allowed the recognition of structural alerts in classical structures of two potent nitrosamines, consistent with their biotransformation.

8.3. QSAR of drug-induced mutagenicity

A set of mutagenicity data (TA100) for 48 nitrated polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (nitro-PAHs) was modelled using the QSAR regression method and OECD principles for QSAR model validation were applied by Gramatica *et al.*¹⁵¹. The proposed multiple linear regression (MLR) models were developed based on two topological molecular descriptors. For the external validation, three different splitting approaches, D-optimal Experimental Design, Self-Organising Maps (SOM) and Random Selection by activity sampling, were applied to the original data set in order to compare these methodologies and to select the best descriptors. The molecular descriptors in the proposed models were very simple. They were 2D-topological descriptors, and could simply be calculated from the molecular graph. The most relevant descriptor is CIC1, an information content index based on the calculation of equivalence classes in the molecular graph, particularly the complementary information content. This descriptor, positively related to mutagenicity, gives information on molecular size and increases with the number of rings and nitro groups in each series of congeners. The information related to the shape of the molecules, correctly correlated to the activity, is encoded by the topological descriptor PW2 (path/walk-2 Randic shape index). Chemicals with a less lin-

ear, more round (circular) shape appear to be the most active. It was again verified by the authors that the number of nitro groups increases the mutagenicity.

Ford and Griffin¹⁵² calculated the relative energetics of arylamine N-hydroxylation and N-O-heterolysis ($\text{ArNH}_2 \rightarrow \text{ArNHOH} \rightarrow \text{ArNH}^+$) for condensed systems of two, three and four rings using semi-empirical AM1 molecular orbital theory. They found that the logarithms of the bacterial mutagenicities of these polycyclic aromatic amines appeared to increase linearly with the calculated stabilities of the corresponding nitrenium ions. Trieff *et al.*¹⁵³ performed a QSAR study of aromatic amines using multiple regression analysis based on a series of 19 aromatic amines. Aromatic amines had been previously measured in *Salmonella typhimurium* strains TA98 and TA100 with the addition of S9 from Aroclor 1254-induced rat liver. The authors found three major factors affecting mutagenicity. The factors are as follows: lipophilic character, position of the amine group, and whether it is free or acetylated. Mutagenicity was shown to increase with lipophilicity. On the other side, mutagenicity is reduced when the amine or acetamido position is *ortho* to the junction because of steric hindrance in biotransformation compared with a non-*ortho* isomer. Mutagenicity is also decreased by the acetylation of the amine group, probably because the acetyl group needs to be first split off before oxidation of the amine group to -NHOH.

A QSAR model was derived for 188 congeners including some of the MAAs by Debnath *et al.*¹⁵⁴. The main determinants of mutagenicity are the hydrophobicity and the E_{LUMO} calculated using the AM1 method. The findings were as follows: chemicals possessing three or more fused rings possess much greater mutagenic potency than compounds with one or two fused rings. In a similar approach applied to 88 aromatic and heteroaromatic amines including monocyclic amines acting on *S. typhimurium* TA98 with S9, and 67 amines acting on TA100 with S9, mutagenicity was found to be linearly dependent on hydrophobicity, the energy of the HOMO, and the energy of the LUMO of the amine¹⁵⁵. The topological sub-structural molecular design (TOPS-MODE) approach has been applied to the study of mutagenic properties in a heterogeneous set of dental monomers by Gonzalez *et al.*¹⁵⁶. The performed model was able to

describe close to 90% of the experimental variance in the values for mutagenic activity of 41 dental monomers through genetic algorithm. Finally, the TOPS-MODE approach was used to derive the contribution of different fragments to the mutagenic activity. This developed model showed that an increase in the carbon linear chain leads to an increase in the mutagenic activity. This affirmation was based on the analysis of the set of fragment from F1 to F3 where an increase in methyl group in each fragment increases the contribution to the property from 0.109 to 0.799. Yet, when the branching of the fragments is increased, the contribution to the mutagenic property is minor as was observed in the fragments F4 and F5. The authors observed that ramification in the groups of the linear aliphatic chain causes sudden increase in the activity. The fragments F3, F4, F5 have the same number of carbons (almost the same hydrophobicity), but very different contributions. Finally, when a bromine atom appears in some fragments, their mutagenic activity increases (i.e. F16, F17). According to their study, all new dental monomers used for forming dental resins should not possess halogens in their structure.

8.4. QSAR of cardiovascular toxicity

8.4.1. QSAR of hERG K⁺ blockers

To accelerate the drug discovery process, early prediction of human ether a-go-go (hERG) K⁺ channel affinity of drug candidates is becoming an important aspect. Roy and Ghosh¹⁵⁷ developed QSTR models with ETA indices for hERG K⁺ channel blocking activity of diverse functional drugs using different chemometric tools like factor analysis followed by multiple linear regression (FA-MLR), stepwise regression and partial least squares. The ETA models were compared with those developed with a pool of other topological indices. It was found that on using ETA parameters along with non-ETA ones, there was a considerable increase in the quality of the models. The ETA model suggests that hERG channel blocking increases with the increase of molecular bulk and electron richness and decreases with the increase of functionalities of the carboxylic acid group and the aliphatic tertiary nitrogen fragment.

2D-QSTR analysis was performed on a dataset of 68 molecules having hERG K⁺ channel blocking activity by

Garg *et al.*¹⁵⁸ using electrotopological, thermodynamic, ADMET, graph theoretical descriptors to derive quantitative models. A statistically significant QSTR model was derived using genetic function approximation methodology. Toxicophore models were generated using HypoGen module in "Catalyst". Three important features for hERG K⁺ channel blockers were identified by the authors. These were (i) hydrophobic group (HP), (ii) ring aromatic group (RA) and (iii) hydrogen bond acceptor lipid group (HBAI). The most predictive hypothesis (Hypo 1), consisting of these three features had the best correlation coefficient of 0.820, a low rms deviation of 1.740, and a high cost difference of 113.50. The hypothesis Hypo 1 was validated by a test set consisting of 12 molecules and also by cross-validation at 95% confidence level. The model was a useful framework for understanding binding, and gave structural insight into the specific protein – ligand interactions responsible for affinity.

Binary QSAR models were developed by Thai and Ecker¹⁵⁹ with threshold values at IC₅₀ = 1 and 10 μM, respectively. Models were generated using two different sets of descriptors : one set comprising 32 P_VSA descriptors and the other one utilizing a set of descriptors identified out of a large set via a feature selection algorithm. For the full dataset, the power for classification of hERG blockers was 82–88%, which meets prior classification models. The models can be best used in lead optimization programs for shaping combinatorial libraries in order to decrease the risk for hERG activity.

8.4.2. QSAR of other cardiovascular toxicity (except hERG K⁺ channel blockers)

Frid and Matthews¹⁶⁰ performed a QSAR study to predict drug-related cardiac adverse effects (AEs). Three programs were used. There were BioEpisteme™, MC4PC, and Leadscape Predictive Data Miner. QSAR models were constructed for 9 cardiac AE clusters affecting Purkinje nerve fibers (arrhythmia, bradycardia, conduction disorder, electrocardiogram, palpitations, QT prolongation, rate rhythm composite, tachycardia, and Torsades de pointes) and 5 clusters affecting the heart muscle (coronary artery disorders, heart failure, myocardial disorders, myocardial infarction, and valve disorders). The models were based on a database of post-marketing AEs linked to 1632 chemical structures. The results revealed that the three

programs were complementary and predictive performances using any single positive, consensus two positives, or consensus three positives were as follows, respectively : 70.7%, 91.7%, and 98.0% specificity; 74.7%, 47.2%, and 21.0% sensitivity; and 138.2, 206.3, and 144.2 χ^2 . In addition, a prospective study using AE data from the US Food and Drug Administration's (FDA's) MedWatch Program showed 82.4% specificity and 94.3% sensitivity. Furthermore, the authors conducted an external validation study using 18 drugs with serious cardiotoxicity not considered in the models and obtained 88.9% sensitivity.

8.5. QSAR of drug-induced acute mammalian toxicity

Lipnick *et al.*¹⁶¹ developed QSAR models and established non-linear relationships (parabolic or bilinear) to describe the baseline toxicity (narcosis mechanism) of 108 chemicals retrieved from Register of Toxicology Effects of Chemical Substances (RTECS). Wolf *et al.*¹⁶² used the lethal narcosis QSARs as taken from Lipnick *et al.*¹⁶¹ for calculation of the baseline toxicity. On the basis of calculated and experimental RTECS values for acute oral toxicity (LD₅₀) and acute inhalation toxicity (LC₅₀), the toxicity ratio (TR) was calculated as the ratio of the calculated baseline toxicity over the experimentally determined value. A TR-value of approximately one indicates baseline toxicity. A TR-value greater than one indicates excess toxicity due to the existence of a more specific mechanism of action. A TR-value less than one could indicate rapid hydrolysis and/or biotransformation of the parent compound by the organism to non-toxic metabolites. Wolf *et al.*¹⁶² concluded that if baseline toxicity is observed through inhalation exposure, it is also expected to occur through oral exposure. In case of a more specific toxicity, the calculated oral baseline toxicity can be used to determine upper exposure limits. The authors found that baseline toxicity could be expected for alcohols, acids, ketones, and one-ring aromatics. Aldehydes and amines show excess toxicity, whereas simple aliphatic hydrocarbons have miscellaneous mechanisms of action, mostly depending upon their electrophilic properties. Due to their relative instability, esters may show less than baseline toxicity. Most of the studies correlate acute toxicity values with hydrophobicity. Jackel and Klein¹⁶³ investigated aliphatic and aromatic amino-com-

pound in order to show whether there is a difference in the predictive power of $\log P$ for the two groups of chemicals. It was found that toxicity data of aliphatic monoamines are sufficiently described by a bilinear $\log P$ -dependent equation. On the other hand, polyamines require a fragment-descriptor of the polyfunctionality. The best QSAR model for anilines is based on parabolic hydrophobic ($\log P$), steric (MV, molecular volume) and electronic (LUMO, energy of the Lowest Unoccupied Molecular Orbital) parameters. Nendza¹⁶⁴ investigated 20 phenylurea derivatives with LD₅₀ values taken from RTECS to find out the importance of hydrophobic and electronic parameters. The author investigated the contribution of $\log P$ to acute toxicity and concluded that several substances having electron-withdrawing substituents on the phenyl ring are underestimated. These observations suggested the author to include also the electronic parameters in the study. The combination of $\log P$ and hardness (HD) yielded a highly significant relationship ($r^2 = 0.830$). Another significant relationship was derived on the basis of $\log P$ (parabolic relationship) and the ionisation potential (IP) ($r^2 = 0.810$). The model based solely on lipophilicity underestimated their toxicity. The added consideration of electronic properties (HD or IP) resulted in a better agreement between the observed and estimated LD₅₀ values.

Cronin *et al.*¹⁶⁵ developed a QSAR for the toxicity of pyridine derivatives to mice. Cronin *et al.* performed the study based on two physico-chemical parameters which were considered to be significant for the investigated effect: one is $\log P$ and the other one is LUMO. The QSAR analysis showed that the toxicity of the pyridines and bipyridines was well described ($r^2 = 0.848$) by hydrophobicity ($\log P$) and electrophilicity (LUMO). The model was developed by excluding one outlier, 3-hydroxy-N-oxide-pyridine, which was underestimated. The authors concluded that pyridine and its alkyl-substituted derivatives were probably acting by a narcosis mechanism of toxic action; some derivatives, notably the N-oxide, appeared to be acting by a more toxic mechanism, probably electrophilic in nature. The acute oral mammalian toxicity of a diverse set of 115 substituted anilines was investigated by Johnson and Jurs¹⁶⁶. Descriptors were generated from MOPAC PM3 optimised conformations. A QSAR model was built by using a neural network model-

ling approach. The subsequent structural descriptors (after genetic algorithm selection) were included in the best model: fifth-order valence cluster molecular connectivity, flexibility index, minimum electrophilic superdelocalizability, atomic charge weighted fractional positive surface area, sum of the charges on donatable hydrogens/total molecular surface area. The model had the satisfactory statistical characteristics: a training set root mean square (RMS) error of 0.233 log unit and a prediction set RMS error of 0.238 log unit.

QSAR models were derived for the acute oral toxicity of 51 organophosphorus pesticides by Devillers¹⁶⁷. Additionally nine chemicals are selected from the literature for external validation. The autocorrelation method was used to describe the compounds. The derived autocorrelation vectors represented lipophilicity, MR, H-Bonding Acceptor (HBA) and H-Bonding Donor (HBD). The model was developed by using the non-linear estimation by Iterative PLSs (NIPALS) algorithm. To boost the quality of the toxicity predictions, attempts were made to derive a non-linear QSAR model from a three-layer feed forward neural network trained by different algorithms. The algorithms are back-propagation, conjugate-gradient descent, quasi-Newton, Levenberg-Marquardt, quick propagation, and delta-bar-delta algorithm – separately or in combination. Good results were obtained with four hydrophobicity variables, one MR variable, one HBA and one HBD variable as input neurons. The best results were obtained with an 8/4/1 ANN model trained with the back-propagation and conjugate gradient descent algorithms. The RMS residual for the training and test set was equal to 0.29 and 0.26, respectively.

Lessigiarska *et al.*¹⁶⁸ developed Quantitative Structure-Activity-Activity relationship (QSAAR) to predict acute mammalian toxicity. *In vitro* toxicity data were collected from the Multicentre Evaluation of *in vitro* Cytotoxicity (MEIC) database. Data for rat, mouse and human toxicity of the same chemicals were also collected from the MEIC. For the QSAR development, $\log P$, aqueous solubility, and approximately 250 different quantum-chemical, topological and charge descriptors were calculated. QSAAR analysis revealed that HLD (human toxicity represented as the acute oral lethal dose) was correlated best with the mouse and rat *in vivo* toxicity ($r^2 = 0.739$). When H-bond donors and Kier benzene-likeness index (measure of molecular aromaticity) were added, the re-

sults improved. The rat LD₅₀ values are correlated best with the toxicity to rat hepatocytes ($r^2 = 0.661$). Adding the number of six-membered rings or molecular polarizability improved the correlation. The first parameter may be related to the size and/or shape of the molecule. The second one might influence the transport or distribution of the chemicals across cell membranes. The QSAR for rat LD₅₀ included the hydrophobicity factor, the electrotopological state descriptor and the number of six-membered rings.

8.6. QSAR of drug-induced prenatal developmental/reproductive toxicity

Due to imprecise, complex endpoints and lack of reproductive toxicology data, QSAR modelling of reproductive toxicology is difficult. A small number of QSAR studies have been performed by some research groups. Therefore, QSAR studies should be encouraged in the reproductive toxicology field. Here, we explain some reported QSAR models of reproductive toxicology based upon endpoints.

8.6.1. Local QSAR models

Developmental toxicity in mouse whole embryo culture assay has been reported for acetic acid (AA) and a series of ten haloacetic acids (HA). Benchmark concentrations (BC_m) are calculated as the lower 95% confidence limit of molar acid concentration producing a 5% increase in embryos with neural tube defects. Calculated potency is used for development of QSAR by Richard and Hunter¹⁶⁹. The best overall regression model was obtained for the ten haloacids (excluding AA). Toxicity is related to the energy of the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (E_{LUMO}) (which is a measure of electrophilicity of a molecule) and acid dissociation constant (pK_a) with a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.97$. This QSAR suggested a common basis for the mechanism of HA activity, which would imply additivity for mixtures of these acids. Examination of QSARs for subsets of the total data set (e.g. monohaloacids) highlighted parameter relationships embedded in the total QSAR, helping to untie the separate contributions of E_{LUMO} and pK_a to the overall potency. The relevance of these parameters was discussed in terms of postulated mechanisms of developmental toxicity involving changes in intercellular pH and redox metabolism. The resulting QSAR model offers possible in-

sight into the mechanism of embryo toxicity which will help to understand the more complex, *in vivo* teratogenicity problem.

The acute lethality of 36 semicarbazides and thiosemicarbazides was evaluated using the Frog Embryo Teratogenesis Assay : *Xenopus* (FETAX). Lethality [$\log(LC_{50})$, LC₅₀ stands for concentration exhibiting lethality for 50% of the observations] of acid hydrazides was modelled by using the 'dynamic' QSAR method by Mekenyan *et al.*¹⁷⁰. The assumed mode of action, osteolathyrism, was defined by the failure of connective tissue to polymerize properly due to interference with lysyl oxidase. Conformer screenings were based on parameter distribution according to the frontier orbital energies and volume polarizability, conditioning their reactivity and hydrophobicity, respectively. The best results were obtained by the selection of conformers providing prevailing values of electron acceptor properties. Moreover, the best two-parameter QSARs encompassing all the evaluated compounds incorporate a geometric parameter, the geometric analogue of the Wiener topological index, and the local electronic characteristics of the C=O or C=S group, superdelocalizabilities and charges.

Devillers *et al.*¹⁷¹ performed a QSAR study with adult and developmental toxicity data for 30 organic chemicals (glycols, glycol ethers and xylenes), obtained with the *H. attenuate* assay. Autocorrelation descriptors encoding lipophilicity, molar refractivity, the H-bonding acceptor and donor ability of the molecules and indicator variables were used to derive the QSAR model. A PLS regression analysis was successfully performed to derive the QSAR model. The best PLS results were obtained with H0, H1, H2, H5, MR0, MR1, MR2, MR3, HBA2, HBD0 and nCl descriptors. H5 and MR0 show negative coefficient for endpoints while other descriptors show positive contribution for the endpoint.

8.6.2. Global QSAR models

Combining toxicity information from the Teratogen Information System (TERIS) and the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) guidelines, a new developmental database was compiled by Sussman *et al.*¹⁷². The authors implemented a decision tree modelling procedure, using a Classification and Regression Tree (CART) software and a model ensemble approach termed bagging. Then

they assessed the empirical distributions of the prediction accuracy measures of the single and ensemble-based models, achieved by repeating their modelling experiment many times by repeated random partitioning of the working database. The decision tree developmental SAR models exhibited modest prediction accuracy. Bagging tended to enhance the accuracy of prediction. In addition, the model ensemble approach reduced the variability of prediction measures compared to the single model approach. Further research with data derived from animal species- and endpoint-specific components of an extended and refined FDA/TERIS database has the potential to derive SAR models that would be useful in the developmental risk assessment of the thousands of untested chemicals. This approach was extended by Arena *et al.*¹⁷³. Physico-chemical descriptors of spatial, electronic and lipophilic properties were used to derive SAR models by two modelling approaches, logistic regression and CART. A QSAR model was developed using a developmental database of 293 chemicals (FDA/TERIS). The results showed that both the decision tree and logistic regression-derived developmental SAR models exhibited modest prediction accuracy. Bagging tended to enhance the prediction accuracy and reduce the variability of prediction measures compared to the single model for CART-based models but not consistently for logistic-based models. Prediction accuracy of single logistic-based models was higher than single CART-based models but bagged CART-based models were more predictive.

8.6.3. Oestrogen receptor (ER) binding models

Comparative molecular field analysis (CoMFA), a three-dimensional quantitative structure-activity relationship (3D-QSAR), was used by Walker *et al.*¹⁷⁴ to examine the estrogen receptor (ER) binding affinities of a series of structurally diverse natural, synthetic, and environmental chemical. The CoMFA/3D-QSAR model successfully illustrates that the overall steric and electrostatic properties of structurally diverse ligands for the estrogen receptor are both necessary and sufficient criteria to describe the binding affinity. The ability of the model to accurately predict the ER binding affinity of an external test set of molecules suggests that structure-based 3D-QSAR models may be used to supplement the process of endocrine disruptor identification through prioritization

of novel compounds for bioassay. A newly developed CoMFA technique, the cross-validated r^2 -guided region selection (CoMFA/ q^2 -GRS) method, was used to build a 3D-QSAR for nonsteroidal estrogen receptor (ER) ligands by Sadler *et al.*¹⁷⁵. Ligands included in this study belong to a series of diethylstilbestrol (DES) and indenestrol analogues whose affinities for the mouse ER (mER) were determined in the authors' laboratory. The final model is based on 30 compounds and it produced a q^2 GRS (cross-validated r^2 , guided region selection) of 0.796, as compared to a q^2 of 0.720 for conventional CoMFA, with a standard error of prediction of 0.594 at 3 principal components. This model can be used to visualize steric and electrostatic features of the ligands that correspond with ER binding affinity. The results obtained from the CoMFA steric and electrostatic plots of this model were also compared to information from the ER binding affinities of substituted estradiol analogues.

A series of 45 estrogen agonist derivatives with relative binding affinities measured to the estrogen receptor from *Ratus norvegicus* was used for the quantitative structure-activity relationships by Kurunczi *et al.*¹⁷⁶. An improved minimal topologic difference (MTD) method in partial least-squares (PLS) variant was used for QSAR model development. The spatially assigned analysis of fragment properties can provide receptor site maps, within the limits of the existing series. A steric misfit was found for the steroidal position 2; beneficial hydrophobic and van der Waals (enhanced by high polarizability) interactions were found for the 17R-CHdCH-X group. MTD-PLS mapping results are confirmed by the experimentally derived estradiol-estrogen receptor binding site contacts (based on X-ray crystallography). The results suggest that MTD-PLS method can yield useful results for interactions with receptors of unknown 3D structure and, generally, for the steric rigidity of receptor sites.

Binding of chemicals to the estrogen receptor (ER) is known to be a key mode of action of endocrine disruption effects. Combined QSAR models from discriminant and multilinear regression (MLR) analyses, termed a two-step model, were developed by Akahori *et al.*¹⁷⁷. Models were used to predict the binding potency to human ER $_{\alpha}$ of four chemical groups, alkylphenols, phthalates, diphenylethanes and benzophenones. These groups of chemicals are considered to be significant chemical classes of ER-binders.

The descriptors investigated were calculated following the simulation of docking between the receptor and ligand. Binders were defined as chemicals whose IC_{50} was dependably calculated in a competitive binding assay. The MLR analysis in the second step was studied for the quantitative prediction of the binding affinity of chemicals that were previously discriminated as binders. The q^2 values for alkylphenols and diphenylethanes were 0.75 and 0.74, respectively.

8.6.4. Androgen receptor (AR) binding models

Söderholm *et al.*¹⁷⁸ studied 3D QSAR of 70 structurally and functionally diverse androgen AR-binding compounds using the comparative molecular similarity indices analysis (CoMSIA) method. The compound set consists of 67 nonsteroidal analogues of flutamide, nilutamide, and bicalutamide whose binding mode to AR was unknown. Docking was used to identify the favoured binding modes for the nonsteroidal compounds within the AR ligand-binding pocket (LBP) and to generate the ligand alignment for the 3D QSAR analysis. Additional model validation was done by the CoMSIA maps that were interpreted with respect to the LBP structure. The model takes into account and links the AR LBP structure, docked ligand structures, and the experimental binding activities. The results provide valuable information on intermolecular interactions between nonsteroidal ligands and the AR LBP.

A large data set of 146 natural, synthetic and environmental chemicals belonging to a broad range of structural classes have been tested for their relative binding affinity to the androgen receptor (AR), were used for model development by Zhao *et al.*¹⁷⁹. QSARs were determined using three methods, MLR, radical basis function neural network (RBFNN) and support vector machine (SVM). Five descriptors, accounting for hydrogen-bonding interaction, distribution of atomic charges and molecular branching degree, were selected from a heuristic method to build predictive QSAR models. Comparison of the results obtained from three models showed that the SVM method exhibited the best overall performances, with a RMS error of 0.54 log (RBA) units for the training set, 0.59 for the test set, and 0.55 for the whole set. Moreover, six linear QSAR models were constructed by the authors for some specific families based on their chemi-

cal structures. Lill *et al.*¹⁸⁰ investigated the influence of induced fit of androgen receptor binding pocket on free energies of ligand binding. On the basis of a novel alignment procedure using flexible docking, molecular dynamics simulations, and linear-interaction energy analysis, Markus and co-workers simulated the binding of 119 molecules representing six compound classes. The superposition of the ligand molecules emerging from the combined protocol served as input for *Raptor*, a receptor-modelling tool based on multidimensional QSAR allowing for ligand-dependent induced fit. Throughout the study, protein flexibility was explicitly accounted for by the authors. The model converged at a cross-validated $r^2 = 0.858$ (88 training compounds) and yielded a predictive $r^2 = 0.792$ (26 test compounds), thereby predicting the binding affinity of all compounds close to published experimental value.

8.7. QSAR of drug-induced skin sensitization, corrosion and irritation

QSARs for skin irritation potential were studied using twenty-four phenols by Hayashi *et al.*¹⁸¹ based on the hypothesis that skin irritation is induced by reaction of phenols with macromolecules present in epidermal and dermal levels of the skin. The absolute hardness (N) calculated from HOMO (the highest occupied molecular orbital) and LUMO (the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital) energy levels for reactivity, and log P for permeability were used as descriptors. Using these descriptors, the authors built a regression function to the set of skin irritation scores obtained from an *in vivo* study, which allowed derivation of equations ($r = 0.85$). The equations were verified with six additional phenols, showing good correlations with the expected skin irritation scores.

A QSAR was derived based on mouse local lymph node assay (LLNA) data for eleven aliphatic aldehydes, one α -ketoester and four α,β -diketones by Roberts *et al.*¹⁸². Skin sensitization to aldehydes and ketones, which can sensitize by covalent binding to skin protein via Schiff base formation, present QSARs based on the Taft σ^* parameter to model reactivity and log P to model hydrophobicity. All of the data were reanalysed together in a stepwise self-consistent way using the parameters log P (octanol/water) and $\Sigma\sigma^*$, the latter being the sum of Taft σ^* values for the two groups R and R' in RCOR'. The

QSAR was found to be well predictive for LLNA data on a series of α,γ -diketones and it correctly predicts the nonsensitizing properties of simple dialkylketones. It was shown to meet all of the criteria of the OECD principles for applicability within regulatory practice. The authors identified that sensitization potential are dependent solely on differences in chemical reactivity and partitioning.

QSAR models for skin sensitization were developed by Li *et al.*¹⁸³ using LLNA data of structurally diverse compounds. The descriptors used to generate these models were derived from the 4D-molecular similarity paradigm and were referred to as universal 4D-fingerprints. The statistical methods used to build the models are logistic regression (LR) and partial least-squares-coupled logistic regression (PLS-LR), which proved to be effective tools for studying skin sensitization measures expressed in the two categorical terms of sensitizer and non-sensitizer. QSAR models with low values of the Hosmer-Lemeshow goodness-of-fit statistic, χ^2_{HL} , were significant and predictive. For the training set, the cross-validated prediction accuracy of the logistic regression models ranges from 77.3% to 78.0%, whereas that of the PLS-logistic regression models ranges from 87.1% to 89.4%. For the test set, the prediction accuracy of logistic regression models ranges from 80.0% to 86.7%, whereas that of the PLS-logistic regression models ranges from 73.3% to 80.0%. The QSAR models were made up of 4D-fingerprints related to aromatic atoms, hydrogen-bond acceptors, and atoms with negative partial charges.

The support vector machine (SVM) method was used to develop a nonlinear binary classification model of skin sensitization for a diverse set of 131 organic compounds by Ren *et al.*¹⁸⁴. Six descriptors were selected by stepwise forward discriminant analysis (LDA) from a diverse set of molecular descriptors calculated from molecular structures alone. These six descriptors could reflect the mechanic relevance to skin sensitization and were used as inputs of the SVM model. The nonlinear model developed from SVM algorithm outperformed LDA, which indicated that SVM model was more reliable in the recognition of skin sensitizers. The proposed method is very useful for the classification of skin sensitizers. The proposed LDA discriminant function could provide some insight into what structural features are related to the skin sensitization. The authors showed that the SVM method

can be used as a very promising tool for classification due to the embodying of the principle of structural risk minimization (SRM).

8.8. Genotoxicity

Halogenated aliphatic compounds were evaluated for toxic and genotoxic effects in the somatic mutation and recombination test employing *Drosophila melanogaster*. The tested chemicals included chlorinated, brominated and iodinated; mono-, di- and tri-substituted; saturated and unsaturated alkanes. A QSAR model was established by Chroust *et al.*¹⁸⁵ for the genotoxicity accessed by the number of twin spots. The two-component PLS model explained 90% (70% cross-validated) of quantitative variance of the genotoxicity data. The most important parameters quantitatively correlating with the genotoxicity data captured the steric properties of the compounds: moment of inertia (M3s), principal axis of moment of inertia (M31) and ellipsoidal volume (EV); hydrophobic properties: total lipole (LIP), hydrophobicity integrity moment (ID1) and electronic properties: total dipole (DIP) and local interaction energy minimum distances (D12 and D13). The exposure of testing organisms to the compounds with large ellipsoidal volume and moments of inertia, but small total lipole, integrity moment, dipole moment and local interaction energy minimum distances results in the largest number of twin mutations. Typical representatives of this group of chemicals are 1,2-dihalogenated ethanes: 1,2-dichloroethane, 1,2-dibromoethane and 1-bromo-2-chloroethane: showing the highest level of genotoxicity within the group of 17 tested chemicals. 1,2-Dihaloalkanes are genotoxic through modification at ring nitrogens in DNA, primarily at the N7 of guanine and N1 of adenine. Nucleophilic superdelocalizability calculated by quantum mechanics appears to be a good parameter for prediction of both toxicity and genotoxicity effects of halogenated aliphatic compounds.

A QSAR study was performed by Tekiner-Gulbas *et al.*¹⁸⁶ with 21 derivatives of 2,5-disubstituted benzoxazole and benzimidazole (**1**) which were tested for their genotoxic activity in the *Bacillus subtilis* assay. The QSAR study revealed that structural parameters $IY_{C_2H_4}$ and IY_{CH_2O} , indicating the bridge elements between the phenyl moiety and the fused ring system at position 2 and the quantum chemical parameter (ΔE), showing the dif-

ference between HOMO and LUMO energies, were significant for enhancing the genotoxic activity in these compounds. In addition, the substituent effects on positions R and R₁ were found important for the activity as well as holding a substituent possessing a maximum length with a minimum width property on position R₁ as alkyl groups. On the other hand, substituting position R with an electron-donating group instead of electron-withdrawing group increased the genotoxic activity.

8.9. QSAR of miscellaneous toxicity

8.9.1. QSAR of apoptotic effect

Zhang *et al.*¹⁸⁷ developed a QSAR model to interpret the relationships between apoptotic effects and chemical structures to identify the immune toxicology mechanism. By the use of a simple *in vitro* toxicological assay, the measured apoptotic parameter (EC₅₀) was used in a QSAR to interpret the apoptotic effects of 25 substituted benzenes. The apoptotic effects of all tested substituted aromatic chemicals with *Carassius auratus* lymphocytes were confirmed by DNA ladder and nucleus condensation. For both chlorobenzenes and PCBs, the EC₅₀ values increase with increasing the number of Cl atoms in the molecule. This result reflects that probably the increased π - π conjugation of the C-Cl bonds lowers the molecular reactivity. Furthermore, the apoptotic EC₅₀ data were best correlated with the dipole moment (μ) and the energy of the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (E_{LUMO}). This result implies that the electronic descriptors play the crucial role in the interaction. The different signs with these two parameters indicate that the dipole moment contributes positively and the E_{LUMO} contributes negatively to the molecular cytotoxicity. The positive dipole moment effect suggests that these chemicals may engage in certain polar or dipole-dipole type of interaction with the target in cells. The dependence on the electronic E_{LUMO} factor of the established correlation suggests that during the apoptotic process, the ROS (reactive oxygen species) produced by cells acts as a Lewis base in substituted nucleo-

philic reactions with toxic chemicals behaving as an electron acceptor.

8.9.2. QSAR of photo-induced toxicity

A few QSAR models were established by Wang *et al.*¹⁸⁸ for photo-induced toxicity of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) to two aquatic species. Partial least squares (PLS) regression and molecular structural parameters calculated by density functional theory (DFT) was employed for model development. Two QSAR models were established and their high R^2 and Q^2_{CUM} values indicated their acceptable goodness-of-fit, robustness and internal predictive power. The descriptors that describe the partition behaviour, light absorbance, and generation of reactive free radicals were found to be successful in modelling the photo induced toxicity by Wang *et al.* The average molecular polarizability (α), energy gap (E_{GAP} or ΔE) between the energy of the LUMO and the HOMO, lowest triplet excitation energy (E_{T1}) and vertical electron affinity at the lowest excited triplet (VEA_{T1}) were the main molecular structural factors, identified by the authors. Polarizability which determines the partition of PAHs between water and lipid governs the photo-induced toxicity of selected PAHs. The authors identified that the photo-induced toxicity increased with the decreasing of E_{GAP} probably due to better spectral overlap. The parameter, VEA_{T1} that characterises the ability of PAH anion radical (PAH⁻) generation from excited triplet state PAH (³PAH*), is also related with the photo-induced toxicity. This investigation gave more insight into the photo-induced toxicity mechanism and assesses the applicability of various DFT-based descriptors to toxicological QSARs.

8.9.3. QSAR of olfactory mucosal (OM) toxicity

Partial least squares projection to latent structures with discriminant analysis (PLS-DA) was built by Carlsson *et al.*¹²³ using OM toxicity data of a number of 2,6-dichlorinated benzene derivatives. Physicochemical properties positively correlated with olfactory mucosal toxicity were identified as molecular dipolar momentum and the electronic properties of the substituent. Inversely correlated descriptors were variables describing the hydrophobicity, electronic properties of the molecule such as electron affinity and the electronic charge on the primary

carbon. Carlsson *et al.* identified that the PLS-DA model showed a 2,6-dichlorinated benzene derivative with a large, polar, and strong electron withdrawing substituent in the primary position has the potential of being a potent OM toxicant. Most certainly, a combination of hydrophilic, lipophilic, steric, and electronic properties, hydrogen bonding, and three-dimensional structure will determine the probability for a specific toxicity measured *in vivo*. Strong electron-withdrawing substituents, such as nitro and methylsulphonyl groups, working through resonance, field, and/or inductive effects would favour a high reactivity of the benzene derivatives for nucleophilic reactions (e.g. a CYP-catalyzed arene oxide formation).

9. QSAR of chemical and pharmaceutical toxicity to the environment

For the ease of discussion, we divide this section in different parts.

9.1. QSAR of aquatic and marine organism-related toxicity

Here, we discuss different QSAR models of aquatic and related toxicity.

9.1.1. *Tetrahymena pyriformis* :

Kar *et al.*¹⁸⁹ used a quantitative topological molecular similarity (QTMS) method to develop models for toxicity of aldehydes to the ecologically important species *Tetrahymena pyriformis*. QTMS descriptors and the lipid-water partition coefficient ($\log K_{ow}$) were used as predictor variables. The QTMS descriptors were calculated at different levels of theory including AM1, HF/3-21G(d), HF/6-31G(d), B3LYP/6-31+G(d,p), B3LYP/6-311+G(2d,p) and MP2/6-311+G(2d,p). The QTMS method begins with the notion that each molecule serves as a collection of atomic attractors (nuclei) surrounded by a sea of charge density. A bond path exists between each pair of atoms and along this bond path there lies a saddle point which is also known as the BCP (bond critical point). Based on overall validation parameters, model 55 at the HF/6-31G(d) level, emerged as the best model among the developed 58 models. The results also suggest that lipophilicity plays the dominant role in describing the aldehydes toxicity. However, electronic factors are also important for the predictability of the models. The advantage of this QTMS method is that it reveals the active

region of the substituted aldehydes. The model based on factors scores of QTMS descriptors of different bonds was able to identify the important fragment (aldehyde functionality) responsible for the mediation of toxicity of aromatic aldehydes as corroborated by their established mechanism of toxicity.

Roy and Ghosh¹⁹⁰ modelled toxicity of nitrobenzene derivatives to *Tetrahymena pyriformis* with extended topochemical atom (ETA) indices. The ETA relations showed positive contributions of molecular bulk (size), halogen and additional nitro-substitutions in the nitrobenzene ring and negative contributions of the substituents like methyl and hydroxymethyl groups to the toxicity. Roy and Ghosh¹⁹¹ developed QSTR models for the toxicity of 384 diverse aromatic compounds to *Tetrahymena pyriformis* using ETA indices and compared the ETA models with those derived from various non-ETA topological descriptors and combined set of descriptors encompassing the ETA and non-ETA parameters. Different statistical analyses (factor analysis followed by multiple linear regression (FA-MLR), stepwise regression and partial least squares (PLS)) were performed to develop various models. From the best models involving ETA parameters, Roy and Ghosh observed that functionality of halogen atoms (hydrophobicity), volume parameter (bulk) and nitrogen containing functionalities (polarity) were important for developing QSTR models for the diverse aromatic compounds. Roy and Ghosh concluded that the ETA descriptors are sufficiently rich in chemical information to encode the important structural features. Toxicity of 49 selected aliphatic amines and aminoalkanols was evaluated in the static *Tetrahymena pyriformis* population growth impairment assay. A high-quality 1-octanol/water partition coefficient-dependent QSAR was developed for alkanamines by Sinks *et al.*¹⁹². Excess toxicity, indicated by potency greater than predicted for non-polar narcotic alkanols, was associated with both classes of test chemicals. Moreover, the aminoalkanols were found to be more toxic than the corresponding alkanamines. This QSAR represented the amine narcosis mechanism of toxic action. However, several structure-toxicity features were observed for this class of chemicals. Hydrocarbon branching next to the amino moiety resulted in decreased toxicity. Aminoalkanol alters lipid metabolism in *T. pyriformis*. The aliphatic amines are more toxic than the alcohols.

While the issue of amine toxicity was clouded by pH effects, aliphatic amines appear to have their own mechanism of action, amine narcosis. Like the nonpolar narcosis exhibited by the alcohols, amine narcosis is a physical and reversible mechanism.

A QSTR model was developed by Jalali-Heravi and Kyani¹⁹³ for a large group of 268 substituted benzene derivatives using mechanistically interpretable descriptors. Toxicity was tested to the ciliated *Tetrahymena pyriformis*. The shuffling-adaptive neuro fuzzy inference system (Shuffling-ANFIS) was successfully applied to select the important factors affecting the toxicity of substituted benzenes to *T. pyriformis*. The results of the proposed model were compared with the model of linear-free energy response surface and the principal component analysis Bayesian-regularized neural network (PCA-BRANN) trained using the same data. The model shows a better statistical parameter in comparison with the previous models. Five descriptors namely octanol-water partition coefficient ($\log P$), bond information content (BICO), number of R-CX-R (C-026), eigenvalue sum from Z-weighted distance matrix (SEigZ) and fragment based polar surface area (PSA) selected by Shuffling-ANFIS reveal the role of hydrophobicity, electronic and steric interactions in the mechanism of toxic action. Sequential zeroing of weights (SZW) as a sensitivity analysis method revealed that the hydrophobicity and electronic interactions play a major role in toxicity of these compounds. Satisfactory results ($q^2 = 0.828$ and RMSE = 0.348) were obtained which indicate that the Shuffling-ANFIS-ANN technique is able to model a diverse chemical class with more than one mechanism of toxicity by using simple and interpretable descriptors.

A QSAR study was performed by Laszlo and Beteringhe¹⁹⁴ for aromatic compounds with toxic effect on *Tetrahymena pyriformis*. The study revealed the existence of two classes of compounds - with and without hydrogen bonds. For the compounds with hydrogen bonds, "moment of inertia B" and "QSPR of percentage of mass fragments" are molecular characteristics with a powerful influence on toxicity values, and $\log K_{ow}$ has a moderate influence. For compounds without hydrogen bonds, "bonds number-weighted total energy" and "LUMO-HOMO gap-weighted molecular volume" are the molecular characteristics with a powerful effect on toxicity values, and topological descriptor AAA has a moderate effect. The

results reveal that toxicity is proportional to the size of the molecules and is correlated with the presence of OH, NO₂, and Cl groups, grafted on the benzenic ring and is temperately correlated with the $\log K_{ow}$ value. The AAA descriptor is useful for the description of toxicity of aromatic derivatives having different substituents grafted on the aromatic ring through the stereoelectronic effects induced by them.

Toxicity data for the 50% growth inhibitory concentration against *Tetrahymena pyriformis* for 42 alkyl- and halogen-substituted nitro- and dinitrobenzenes were obtained experimentally. Hydrophobicity and the molecular orbital properties, the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital energy (E_{LUMO}) and maximum acceptor superdelocalizability (A_{max}), were used to develop QSAR models by Cronin *et al.*¹⁹⁵. The nitrobenzenes were thought to elicit their toxic response through multiple (and mixed) mechanisms. No high-quality relationship was observed between toxicity and hydrophobicity, or E_{LUMO} , individually. Halogen- and/or alkyl-substituted nitroaromatic compounds exhibited excess toxicity. Separate hydrophobicity-dependent QSARs were developed for the mono- and dinitro derivatives by Cronin *et al.* However, the most successful approach was two-parameter QSAR, or response surface analysis, which resulted in high-quality models based on measures of hydrophobicity and electrophilicity without reference to mechanism of action.

9.1.2. *Daphnia magna* :

Kar and Roy¹⁹⁶ modelled a large diverse group of 297 chemicals for their toxicity to *Daphnia magna* using mechanistically interpretable descriptors. Three-dimensional (3D) (electronic and spatial) and two-dimensional (2D) (topological and information-content indices) descriptors along with physicochemical parameter $\log K_{o/w}$ (n-octanol/water partition coefficient) and structural descriptors were used as predictor variables. A global model (involving seven descriptors and three latent variables) was developed which is applicable for diverse classes of chemicals. The developed QSTR model suggests that higher lipophilicity and electrophilicity, less negative charge surface area and presence of ether linkage, hydrogen-bond donor groups and acetylenic carbons are responsible for greater toxicity of chemicals.

The acute toxicity of 20 α -substituted phenylsulphonyl acetates was measured using *Daphnia magna* with a static

method¹⁹⁷. On the basis of physicochemical parameters ($\log K_{ow}$ and aqueous solubility $\log S_w$), the theoretical linear solvation energy relationships (TLSER) and Charge model descriptors, QSARs were developed for the immobilization of *D. Magna* by Liu *et al.*¹⁹⁷. The model indicates that hydrophobicity plays a dominant role on the toxicity. For the TLSER model and the Charge model, the large squared correlation coefficients suggest that the models had good predictive capability. The higher activity of the compounds can be explained with the disruption of van der Waals interactions between lipid and/or protein compounds within the membrane and the possibility of the compounds to form hydrogen bonds with the receptor molecules. Hydrogen bonding has a great influence on the biological activity. Negative influences of the molecular volume, polarizability and the covalent contribution to Lewis basicity show a decrease in the concentration that produces the toxic effect, consequently, and a greater toxicity. A negative influence of V_{mc} , proportional to hydrophobicity of the chemical, may be related to an increased partitioning tendency of the higher lipophilic compound into the membrane of the organism. A negative coefficient of the polarizability term suggests a binding action via dispersion forces, possibly in the polar regions of the receptor molecule.

Toxicities of benzoic acids to *Daphnia magna* were measured and a QSAR model was constructed by Zhao *et al.*¹⁹⁸. The results showed that the toxicity to *Daphnia* decreased in the order of bromo > chloro > fluoro aminobenzoic acids. The results also showed that the toxicity of benzoic acids to *Daphnia* decreased as the pH increased. It is suggested that ionized and non-ionized forms have different toxic responses. The non-ionized forms may play an important role in toxicity because the toxicity of benzoic acids to *Daphnia* greatly decreases as the pH increases. The toxicity of benzoic acids to *Daphnia* may operate through non-polar narcosis, based on the regression results between the toxicities and partition coefficients ($\log P$) and apparent partition coefficients ($\log D$). However, the toxicity cannot be predicted from non-polar baseline models due to the ionized and non-ionized form of benzoic acids has different contributions to toxicity. Compared with the single descriptors, the prediction of toxicity of the benzoic acids was improved remarkably by using $\log P$ with pK_a and $\log P$ with E_{LUMO} .

The authors conclude that the toxicity of benzoic acids may be predicted with reasonable accuracy by hydrophobicity and a parameter to describe ionization. Undoubtedly both the ionized and non-ionized forms of the benzoic acids contribute to the toxicity. Furthermore, it was postulated that a different mechanism of action may be responsible for the toxicity of benzoic acids to organisms with low lipid content.

Toropov and Benfenati¹⁹⁹ examined three types of local graph invariants, the vertex degrees (0EC), the extended connectivity of first order (1EC), and the numbers of paths of length two (P^2), as elementary invariants for construction QSAR models. The authors examined combined invariants, obtained by multiplying one of these three elementary types with another (i.e. [$^0EC.^1EC$], [$^0EC.P^2$], and [$^1EC.P^2$]), as graph invariants. Global invariants were used in the QSAR analyses, codifying the presence and nature of cycles in the molecular structures under consideration. These descriptors were used in one-variable models to predict toxicity toward *Daphnia magna* for a set of pesticides. The authors interpreted that the relationship between the presence of Cl atom and toxicity can explain the toxicity of chlorinated pesticides. The relationship with P atom is likely explaining the toxicity of organophosphates. In the case of descriptors related to a ring, the presence of a three-membered ring is like to be related to increased toxicity. They concluded that the local invariant of the molecular graph, that is equal to the multiplication of vertex degree by number of paths of length 2, is the most appropriate for constructing the optimal descriptors for modelling toxicity toward *D. magna*.

9.1.3. *Vibrio fischeri* :

Roy and Ghosh²⁰⁰ modelled the acute toxicity of 56 phenylsulphonyl carboxylates (**2**) to *Vibrio fischeri*. Principal component factor analysis was used as the data-preprocessing step for the selection of independent variables for the subsequent multiple regression analysis. Use of the ETA indices suggested that negative contributions of steric bulk, branching, functionality of C atom containing R_2 and R_3 substituents, functionality of chloro substituent at X1 position and presence of unsaturation at the substituent(s) on C atom containing R_2 and R_3 substituents, and positive contributions of functionality of O atom

adjacent to R_1 atom and presence of substituents with electronegative atoms at R_2 and R_3 positions. Using factor scores as independent variables, principal component regression analysis was performed and the derived relations are of excellent statistical qualities (Q^2 values being 0.816, 0.828 and 0.848 while R^2 values being 0.894, 0.871 and 0.905 for factor scores derived from ETA, non-ETA and combined matrices respectively). This study suggests that ETA parameters are sufficiently rich in chemical information to encode the structural features contributing significantly to the acute toxicity of phenylsulphonyl carboxylates to *Vibrio fischeri*.

The toxicity of 14 industrially relevant organic chemicals was determined using freshly grown *Vibrio fischeri* bioluminescence inhibition assay²⁰¹. Reliability of octanol-water partition coefficient (K_{ow}), and first-order simple and valence molecular connectivity index ($^1\chi$, $^1\chi^v$)-based regression models for predicting toxicity to *V. fischeri* was studied by Parvez *et al.* (2008). Toxicity determined by *V. fischeri* assay showed good correlations with $\log(K_{ow})$, $^1\chi$, and $^1\chi^v$. This study reflected that $^1\chi$ and $^1\chi^v$ were not sensitive descriptors for polarity. The parameters energy of the highest occupied (E_{HOMO}), lowest unoccupied molecular orbitals (E_{LUMO}), and their difference ($\Delta E = E_{LUMO} - E_{HOMO}$) were more sensitive to polar compounds, hence, these descriptors can be applied for improving the predictions for polar compounds. E_{LUMO} was a good descriptor for compounds engaging in electrophilic reaction and can be used to explain the polar narcotic mechanism of action of anilines and phenols. A single molecular property cannot predict reliable and accurate toxicity values for most of the chemicals. Multivariate regression models utilizing $\log(K_{ow})$ or $^1\chi^v$ along with descriptors, such as, E_{HOMO} , E_{LUMO} or ($E_{LUMO} - E_{HOMO}$) was expected to yield better predictions.

Predictive QSAR models were developed by Schultz *et al.*²⁰² for the logarithm of the 15-min toxicity to the

marine bacterium *Vibrio fischeri* (pT₁₅) using a hydrophobicity term and a term to describe electrophilicity (the energy of the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital, E_{LUMO}). QSARs were developed initially for individual chemical classes by Schultz *et al.* Statistically robust hydrophobic-dependent QSARs were obtained for the haloalcohols and halonitriles. However, a lower quality hydrophobic-dependent equation was observed for diones and only a poor quality hydrophobic-dependent model was developed for chloroesters. These QSARs suggest that four chemical classes exhibit different electrophilic mechanisms of toxic action, as well as different mechanisms occurring in the diones and chloroesters considered. A combination of all four classes revealed a highly predictive QSAR based on both descriptors. According to Schultz *et al.* this predictive model was applicable regardless of chemical classes and does not require a priori identification of mechanisms of action. A novel group contribution method, QSAR, has been developed by Luis *et al.*²⁰³ for ionic liquids to estimate the EC_{50} for *Vibrio fischeri*. The method was based on the prediction of dimensionless ecotoxicity, Y^* , by the summation of the group contributions : cations, anions, and substitutions. The results were statistically sound ($r^2 = 0.925$). The contributions to the QSAR allow one to estimate the influence each group (cations, anions, alkyl chains) has on the EC_{50} . The authors assumed from the interpretation that pyrrolidinium, imidazolium, and pyridinium groups contribute about 3%, 20%, and 33% to the toxicity, respectively. It was concluded that the pyrrolidinium group contributed the least to the toxicity. An additional methyl group in the molecule increased the toxicity by about 7%. The contributions of anions to the toxicity were negative, which means that the presence of anions leads to a decrease in the toxic effect of cations. Bromide (Br^-), dicyanamide ($N(CN)_2^{2-}$), and ethyl sulfate ($C_2H_5SO_4^-$), may be considered as higher toxicity anions in the ionic liquid.

9.1.4. *Rana japonica* :

Roy and Ghosh²⁰⁴ developed QSTR models for the acute lethal toxicity of 51 benzene derivatives to *Rana japonica* using ETA indices. They also compared the ETA relations with non-ETA models derived from different topological indices and physicochemical parameters. Genetic function approximation (GFA) and factor analysis

(FA) were used as the data-pre-processing steps for the development of final multiple linear regression (MLR) equations. The relations developed from ETA descriptors suggest a parabolic dependence of the toxicity on molecular size. Furthermore, the toxicity increases with functionality contribution of chloro substituent and decreases with those of methoxy, hydroxy, carboxy and amino groups. Acute lethal toxicity of 46 benzene derivatives to *Rana japonica* tadpoles was determined. 1-Octanol/water partition coefficient-dependent models were developed to study the toxicity of different categories chemicals by Huang *et al.*²⁰⁵. To model all chemicals, response surface analyses and stepwise multiple regression analyses were performed. A general and robust QSAR model was performed with the combined application of variables reflecting hydrophobicity, electric property, and molecular size respectively using stepwise multiple regression analyses. Because of strong dissociation of carboxyl group greatly decreasing their observed toxicity, on use of $\log D_{ow}$ in instead of $\log K_{ow}$, the quality of the models was greatly improved. The conventional r^2 and cross-validation r^2_{CV} were 0.914 and 0.785, respectively.

9.1.5. *Bufo vulgaris formosus* :

Multivariate linear regression and best subset regression analyses were performed by Yan *et al.*²⁰⁶ for the lethal toxicity, LC_{50} , for 41 organophosphorous pesticides (OPs) found in tadpoles (*Bufo vulgaris formosus*). An equation was developed for all selected OPs, particularly those with comparatively low toxicity levels ($LC_{50} > 4.5$ mM) that accounted for 89.09% of the variability in the toxic effect. The equation indicated that the main contributions to OP toxicity with tadpoles were the electrostatic contribution qH^+ (maximum net positive H atomic charge), spatial autocorrelation (MAT57m) and hydrophobicity ($\log K_{ow}$), with the previous two being the most important parameters. For OPs with high toxicity, however, different structural parameters were introduced. Another equation was developed with $LC_{50} < 4.5$ mM. These equations implied that with different levels of toxicity there could have different mechanisms in the tadpole. Furthermore, the results showed that molecular structural parameters had a particular value in modelling chemical reactivity within a homologous series of compounds.

The model was further improved over changing the thiophosphoryl function $P=S$ into the oxygen analog $P=O$ of OPs, and it shows that for the toxicity mechanism of OPs to tadpoles *in vivo*, the oxygen analog $P=O$ plays the key role. For the highest toxicity of OPs, a subset data consisting of six OPs compounds was of more concern, and the stereoselectivity plays an important role.

9.1.6. *Chlorella vulgaris* :

QSTR models were developed by Xia *et al.*²⁰⁷ with 91 aliphatic and aromatic compounds as well as a small subset of pesticides to algae *Chlorella vulgaris*. The linear (HM) and the nonlinear method radial basis function neural networks (RBFNN) were used to develop the QSTR models. Interpreting the descriptors, the authors prescribed some insight into structural features (molecular surface area, electrostatic repulsion, and hydrogen bonds) related to the toxic action. Finally, a detailed analysis on the model application domain defined the compounds, whose estimation can be accepted with confidence. The results of this study explained the factors affecting toxicity from microcosmic perspective. The HM provides a transparent result for modelling the toxicity which indicates that MSA (Molecular surface area), electrostatic repulsion, and hydrogen bonds factor are closely related to the toxicity.

9.1.7. *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* :

Roy and Popelier²⁰⁸ constructed predictive QSAR models for the toxicity of nitroaromatics to *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. The authors used QTMS descriptors along with electrophilicity index (E_{LUMO}) and lipid/water partition coefficient ($\log K_{ow}$) as predictor variables. The QTMS descriptors were calculated at B3LYP/6-311+G(2d,p) level of theory. QTMS descriptors were employed to complement the deficiency of E_{LUMO} in setting up predictive QSAR models from the view point of external validation. Partial Least Squares (PLS) models were developed by Roy and Popelier²⁰⁸. The results suggest that Bond Critical Point (BCP) descriptors can develop predictive QSAR models for nitroaromatic toxicity to *S. cerevisiae* when used along with E_{LUMO} and $\log K_{ow}$. The diagnostic potential of QTMS descriptors also reveals the importance of the nitro group for nitroaromatic toxicity.

9.1.8. *Scenedesmus obliquus* :

A QSPR model was developed for the 50% effective inhibition concentration of 36 selected substituted benzenes for the algae *Scenedesmus obliquus* by the application of the Characteristic Root Index (CRI) model by Sacan *et al.*²⁰⁹. To increase the predictive power of the CRI-based model, different semi-empirical molecular descriptors calculated by the quantum chemical PM3 method were included : the energy of the highest occupied molecular orbital (E_{HOMO}), the energy of the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (E_{LUMO}), and the dipole moment (μ). E_{LUMO} was the most important parameter, followed by the CRI. E_{LUMO} reflects electronic properties, whereas the CRI reflects hydrophobicity, molecular size, and branching. The statistical robustness of the developed model was validated by the modified jackknife test. The CRI - E_{LUMO} -based model indicates that the toxicity of the studied compounds to the algae is associated mainly with their ability to penetrate to the cell through its cell membrane and with the electronic interactions of the chemicals with the active site of action through a variety of electronic processes.

9.1.9. *Pseudokirchneriella subcapitata* :

QSAR models were established by Huang *et al.*²¹⁰ with the toxicity data of various nitriles to *Pseudokirchneriella subcapitata* using a closed algal toxicity. Two different response endpoints, i.e. dissolved oxygen (DO) production and algal growth rate, were used to evaluate the toxicity of nitriles. In general, the DO endpoint revealed higher inhibitory effects than that from algal growth rate. QSARs were established based on the chemicals' E_{LUMO} values and hydrophobicity ($\log K_{\text{ow}}$). The study reveals that halogen-substituted nitriles were found to be extremely toxic to *P. subcapitata*. With increasing numbers of the halogen atoms, stronger toxicity was observed. The bromine substituent also seems to be more toxic than chlorine substituent. Such relationships may thus be useful in predicting the toxicity of other compounds of the same mode of toxic action. A study reported by Lee and Chen²¹¹ presents the toxicity data of benzoic acid and its derivatives on *Pseudokirchneriella subcapitata*, in terms of EC_{50} and NOEC values. The toxicity of halogenated benzoic acids was found to be directly related to the compound's hydrophobicity. On the other hand, the

number of hydroxyl groups (N_{OH}) had a determinant influence to the toxicity of hydroxybenzoic acids. QSARs were established to correlate the observed toxicity with $\log K_{\text{ow}}$ and N_{OH} values. These statistical correlations are highly significant with the predictive power Q^2 ranging from 0.896 to 0.955.

9.1.10. Fish

Roy and Ghosh²¹² developed QSTR models for fish toxicity of various benzene derivatives from the viewpoint of ecological safety assessment. ETA indices and selected topological descriptors and physicochemical variables were used for model development. The ETA relations showed positive contributions of molecular bulk (size), chloro and hydroxyl substitutions in the benzene ring, and the simultaneous presence of methyl and nitro substitutions to the toxicity. Further, the presence of fluoro and ether functionality, amino or nitro functionality in an otherwise unsubstituted ring, and nitro functionality that is *ortho* to a chloro substituent decreases toxicity. In this study, ETA indices could explore the important chemical information contributing to the fish toxicity of substituted benzenes.

9.1.11. *Pimephales promelas* :

Colombo *et al.*²¹³ used theoretical molecular descriptors to divide 568 organic substances into subsets with toxicity measured for the 96-h lethal median concentration for the Fathead minnow (*Pimephales promelas*). Simple constitutional descriptors such as the number of aliphatic and aromatic rings and a quantum chemical descriptor, maximum bond order of a carbon atom divide compounds into nine subsets. For each subset of compounds, the automatic forward selection of descriptors was applied to construct QSAR models. Significant correlations were achieved for each subset of chemicals and all models were validated with the leave-one-out internal validation procedure ($R^2_{\text{cv}} \approx 0.80$). The results encourage this alternative way for the prediction of aquatic toxicity using QSAR subset models without direct reference to the mechanism of toxic action or the traditional chemical classification. Despite of the fact that all of the subsets contained chemicals acting through various mechanism of action (MOA), the derived QSAR-s showed good predictive quality with $R^2_{\text{cv}} > 0.8$. This QSAR model

can be used to predict the toxicity of a wide range of chemicals. The presented approach codifies knowledge about chemical structure and classifies compounds into univocal chemical classes.

9.2. Rodent toxicity

Quantitative structure-activity-activity relationship (QSAAR) models were developed for the *in vivo* human and rodent toxicity including a combination of toxicity endpoint and structural descriptors as predictor variables by Lessigiarska *et al.*¹⁶⁸. The human peak blood/serum LC₅₀ concentrations were most strongly related to human liver cell toxicity, while the *in vivo* oral human lethal doses were most closely related to the *in vivo* rodent LD₅₀ values. The QSAARs included structural descriptors encoding electronic/reactivity properties, presence of H-bond donors, compound aromaticity, and size/shape properties. QSARs were derived by using structural descriptors accounting for molecular hydrophobicity, size and shape, and electronic properties. These models have the potential to provide useful insights in the development of non-animal (*in vitro* and *in silico*) methods for predicting human and mammalian toxicity. The 50% lethal dose concentration for rats (LD₅₀) was used as the estimation of toxicity *in vivo* to develop 1D QSAR models by Kuz'min *et al.*²¹⁴ on the framework of Simplex representation of molecular structure of 28 nitroaromatic compounds. The results of 1D QSAR analysis show that even the information about the composition of molecules provides the main trends of toxicity changes. The necessity of consideration of substituents' mutual impacts for the development of adequate QSAR models of nitroaromatics' toxicity was demonstrated by the authors. A successful performance of such models was due to their non-additivity, i.e. possibility of taking into account the mutual influence of substituents in benzene ring which plays the governing role for toxicity change and could be mediated through the different C-H fragments of the ring. The contribution of nitro group to the toxicity substantially depends on the presence/absence of other substituents and varies from high-positive to weakly-negative. Hydroxyl and fluorine groups increase toxicity and the presence of methyl group decreases it. Chlorine has unambiguous influence on toxicity.

9.3. Cell line toxicity

QSARs were developed by Liu *et al.*²¹⁵ to predict

toxicity of chlorophenols by correlating LC₅₀ values with five molecular descriptors, chosen to represent lipophilic, electronic and steric effects : the n-octanol/water partition coefficient ($\log K_{ow}$), the constant of Hammett ($\Sigma\sigma$), the acid dissociation constant (pK_a), the first order valence molecular connectivity index (${}^1\chi^v$) and the perimeter of the efficacious section (ΣD_g). The results of the regression analysis showed that $\log K_{ow}$ and ΣD_g were the dominant (canonical) predictive factors in determining toxicity of chlorophenols to the cells during 24 h exposures, while $\log K_{ow}$ was the only dominant predictive factor contributing to toxicity during in 48 h exposures. Comparative molecular field analysis (CoMFA) and comparative molecular similarity indices analysis (CoMSIA) were applied to investigate predictive relationships of the cytotoxicity of chlorophenols and develop visual 3D-QSAR models. The CoMFA model, in which the contribution of the electrostatic field to the biological activity was greater than that of the steric field, exhibited both high consistency and predictability. The CoMSIA model used in this study contained three fields : electrostatic, hydrophobic and steric. The authors interpreted that the presence of chlorine at the 3- and 5-positions favours hydroxylation of the 4-position of chlorophenols. Hydroxylated products can result in the corresponding chlorohydroquinones, which may enhance toxicity and carcinogenicity of chlorophenols. This prediction is consistent with the results of the field contour maps of CoMFA and CoMSIA. With the use of 3D-QSAR : CoMFA and CoMSIA techniques, the authors were able to elucidate toxicological mechanism of the ligand-receptor interaction that can be used to develop testable hypotheses of the mechanism of *in vitro* toxicity of chlorophenols on L929 cells.

9.4. QSAR for predicting bioconcentration factors (BCF)

Zhao *et al.*²¹⁶ built QSAR models with a large data set of 473 heterogeneous chemicals, based on multiple linear regression (MLR), radial basis function neural network (RBFNN) and support vector machine (SVM) methods for predicting BCF. The author also applied a hybrid model which gave better prediction than single models. Among the selected descriptors the following ones, Moriguchi octanol-water partition coefficient ($M \log P$),

Moran autocorrelation (MATS5v) and number of chlorine atoms (SsCl, Cl-089) are closely and directly correlated with the biological activity. The absolute sums of eigenvalues (BEHp2, AEige) and Geary autocorrelation (GATS5v) descriptors are inversely related with BCF, though with a lower linear correlation. Zhao *et al.* showed that log *P* plays the larger role, as expected. Polarizability and electronegativity, in that order, contribute to the model's BCF. SsCl and Cl-089 descriptors contributing to a small extent to modelling BCF refer to the shape and anisotropy of the molecule. The calculated accuracy was of 98%, sensitivity of 96%, and specificity of 100%. Thus, the hybrid model built by Zhao *et al.* performed well as a classifier for "B" and "vB" chemicals. QSAR models were developed by Papa *et al.*²¹⁷ for the prediction of BCF in general and for problematic chemical classes such as highly hydrophobic chemicals. The best descriptor subsets for the models were selected using the Genetic Algorithm-Variable Subset Selection strategy (GA-VSS) and calculations were performed by ordinary least-squares regression. Starting from a data set of 640 compounds (log K_{ow} ranges from -2.34 to 12.66), the authors developed linear QSARs, first, for a data set of 620 compounds (log K_{ow} ranges from -2.34 to 10.35) and second, specifically for 87 highly-hydrophobic chemicals (log K_{ow} range from 6.00 to 10.35). For the first developed model, the selected descriptors highlight the importance of polarizability, hydrogen bonding and chemical dimension in log BCF modelling. In order to model high hydrophobic chemicals, more complex descriptors were used, due probably to the number of different factors affecting this process; 3D-descriptors, and GETAWAY in particular, selected in both the models, seem to be useful in log BCF modelling. H2p, a 3D H-GETAWAY descriptor encodes both the geometrical information and the topological information given by the molecular graph, weighted by selected atomic weights of the toxicants.

Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) are one of the most prevalent and ubiquitous potential persistent organic pollutants. Using the variable selection and modelling based on prediction (VSMP), the molecular electronegativity distance vector (MEDV) derived directly from the molecular topological structures was employed to develop a linear model (MI) between the BCF and two MEDV descriptors of 58 PCBs by Qin *et al.*²¹⁸. The MI model showed good estimation ability with a correlation coefficient

(*r*) of 0.9605 and a high stability with a leave-one-out cross-validation correlation coefficient (*q*) of 0.9564. Main structural factors influencing the BCF of PCBs were the substructures expressed by two atomic groups $>C=$ and $-C=$. 58 PCBs were divided into an "odd set" and "even set" in order to ensure the predicted potential of the MI for the external samples. It was shown that three models, MI, MO for "odd set", and ME for "even set", can be used to predict the BCF of 152 PCBs in which the experimental BCFs are not available. The heuristic method (HM) and support vector machine (SVM) were used to build the linear and nonlinear QSAR models by Liu *et al.*²¹⁹ for the prediction of the fish BCF for 122 diverse nonionic organic chemicals. Both the linear and nonlinear models gave satisfactory prediction results: the square of correlation coefficient R^2 values were 0.929 and 0.953, the root mean square (RMS) error values were 0.404 and 0.331, respectively for the whole dataset. The prediction result of the SVM model was better than that obtained by heuristic method, which proved that SVM was a useful tool in the prediction of the BCF. The authors concluded that (1) the proposed models could identify and provide some insight into what structural features are related to the bioconcentration process of non-ionic organic chemicals and help to improve the understanding for the bioconcentration mechanism of organic compounds. (2) Nonlinear relationship could describe accurately the relationship between the structural parameter and the bioconcentration factors of the studied organic pollutants. (3) SVM proved to be a useful tool in the prediction of the bioconcentration behaviour of organic chemicals.

A quantitative structure-property relationship (QSPR) study was conducted by Roy *et al.*²²⁰ based upon log BCF of 122 non-ionic organic compounds in fish using the ETA indices. Based on the QSAR models, the authors concluded that the ETA indices suggested negative contributions of functionalities of nitro, amino and hydroxy substructures and positive contributions of branching, volume and functionality of chloro substituents.

10. Expert systems

The major criterion of toxicity prediction is to distinguish between toxicologically active and inactive compounds. Multiple mechanisms can lead to the same toxic effect and this complexity requires the availability of pre-

dictive tools that are able to distinguish multiple regions in the activity space. This need has led to the development of so-called expert systems, which try to cover broader structural and activity regions in comparison with the local models. There are a number of commercial or freely available toxicity prediction software packages. They have advantages over the use of traditional QSAR. Expert systems permit for the direct entry of a structure into a piece of software and thus the calculation of an estimate without the requirement to calculate descriptors, re-perform modelling, etc. Many expert systems have been regularly used by regulatory agencies and industry worldwide. In Table 9, we present an overview of different freely available and commercial expert systems to predict endpoints related chemicals and pharmaceutical toxicity.

11. Limitations and difficulties of *in silico* approaches

For the balanced assessment, concentration should be drawn to many limitations which can be found with the application of *in silico* approaches. For predictive QSAR modelling, different limitations are involved. Here, we explain few of them which are the major ones.

(i) Assurance and transparency of the high-quality experimental data used to build the QSAR model are essential. If incorrect molecular structure or erroneous data from toxicology studies of a chemical is introduced into the model, enlargement of that error occurs and it is represented in the prediction.

(ii) The number of QSAR models for organometallics, complex mixtures (e.g. botanical extracts), and high-

Table 9. Overview of different freely available and commercial expert systems (representative list) to predict endpoints related to different toxicities

Sl. no.	Expert system	Manufacturer and website	Descriptions	Endpoints for different toxicity and source of data
1.	TOPKAT TOxicity Prediction by C(K)omputer Assisted Technology	Accelrys Inc. http://www.accelrys.com/products/topkat/	(a) TOPKAT is a statistical expert system (b) QSAR models developed from large heterogeneous databases of toxicological information using substructural fragments and (electro)-topological indices (c) Commercial system	(a) Developmental toxicity potential from FDA/TERIS (b) The program uses a range (Q)SAR models for assessing acute toxicity to FHM and Daphnia (c) TOPKAT comprises two sets of sensitization models that were developed originally by Enslein <i>et al</i> (d) The TOPKAT LD ₅₀ (acute oral toxicity) modelling approach has been used by the Danish EPA in their project to develop QSAR models for evaluation of dangerous properties of around 47000 organic substances on the European Inventory of Existing Commercial chemical Substances (EINECS) list
2.	DEREK for Windows	Lhasa Ltd. http://www.lhasalimited.org/index.php?cat=2&sub_cat=64	(a) Knowledge-based expert system (b) Developed in collaboration with industrial partners, which makes it predictions based on structural alerts, reasoning rules and examples contained within its knowledge base	(a) Currently 21 structural alerts for teratogenicity, or teratogenic endpoints (b) The knowledge base includes four alerts and associated reasoning rules and examples for oestrogenicity. Assay, mechanistic and other relevant data used to support the knowledge

Table-9 (contd)

			in these cases is generally obtained from extensive searching of public domain sources including the primary literature
3. ECOSAR ECOLOGICAL Structure-Activity Relationships	http://www.epa.gov/oppt/exposure/docs/episuiteidl.htm	(a) ECOSAR uses a number of class-specific log K_{ow} -based QSARs to predict the toxicity (both short-term and long-term) of chemicals (b) The software is freely available from the US EPA (downloadable form)	Hazard assessment of environmentally occurring pharmaceuticals to fish, daphnids and green algae using ECOSAR
4. ONCOLOGIC	http://www.epa.gov/oppt/sf/pubs/oncologic.htm	OncoLogic is a desktop computer program that evaluates the likelihood that a chemical may cause cancer	OncoLogic predicts cancer-causing potential by : (a) applying the rules of structure activity relationship (SAR) analysis, (b) mimicking the decision logic of human experts, and (c) incorporating knowledge of how chemicals cause cancer in animals and humans
5. MCASE/ MC4PC	MultiCASE Inc. http://www.multicase.com/products/products.htm	(a) MCASE is a knowledge-based system and developed by Klopman and Rosenkranz (b) MCASE develops QSAR models and evaluates the structural features of a set of non-congeneric molecules and identifies the substructures that may be responsible for the observed activity (c) Commercial system	(a) Models for several fish species are available (blue gill, FHM, rainbow trout, red killifish) (b) There are more than 180 modules covering various areas of toxicology and pharmacology endpoints including skin sensitization currently marketed by MultiCASE Inc. (Cleveland, Ohio, US) (c) Retinoids (76 compounds); developmental toxicity (66 antifungal triazole alcohols; composite dataset of 275 compounds); developmental toxicants (mouse 101, rat 134, rabbit 66, humans 119, hamster 192 compounds); FDA/TERIS developmental toxicity (humans 323 compounds); developmental toxicants in FDA teratogenicity (rabbit 812, rat 1286, mouse 794, miscellaneous mammal 1409 compounds)
6. OSIRIS property explorer	Organic Chemistry Portal http://www.organic-chemistry.org/prog/peo/tox.html	An on-line system which predicts (undefined) reproductive effects on the basis of structural fragments	Fragments developed from the analysis of 3570 compounds with reproductive effects listed in RTECS

Table-9 (contd.)

7.	HazardExpert Pro	CompuDrug Inc. http://www.compu drug.com/	Predicts teratogenicity on the basis of structural fragments	Predict reproductive toxicity
8.	ASTER	http://www.epa.gov/med/ Prods_Pubs/ aster.htm	An integration of a database (ECOTOX database) and a structure-activity based expert system and freely available	Predict aquatic toxicity
9.	PASS	Institute of Biomedical Chemistry of the Russian Academy of Medical Sciences, Moscow http://ibmc.p450.ru/PASS/	Assesses similarity of molecules to those with known activity	(a) Prediction of over 30 endpoints that may be relevant to reproductive toxicity (b) Endpoints (Abortion inducer, alkylator, carcinogenic, DNA intercalator, DNA repair enzyme inhibitor, DNA synthesis inhibitor, DNA topoisomerase ATP hydrolysing Inhibitor, DNA topoisomerase inhibitor, DOPA decarboxylase inhibitor, embryotoxic, oestradiol 17 β -dehydrogenase stimulant, oestrogen agonist, oestrogen antagonist, ER modulator, oestrone sulphatase inhibitor, oestrone sulphotransferase stimulant, fertility enhancer, gynaecological disorders treatment, menopausal disorders treatment, mutagenic, retinoic acid α -receptor agonist, retinoic acid β -receptor agonist, retinoic acid receptor antagonist, retinoid X receptor agonist, retinoid acid receptor agonist, spermicide, teratogen, testosterone agonist, toxic, uterine relaxant, uterine stimulant
10.	OECD (Q)SAR Application Toolbox	OECD, Paris http://www.oecd.org/document/23/0,3343,en_2649_34379_33957015_1_1_1_1,00.html	Allows the user to develop categories and perform read-across, QSAR and trend analyses	A platform that will allow chemical information management, similarity searches and toxicological profiling
11.	TerraQSAR - FHM	http://www.terrabase-inc.com	Commercial software	It is a standalone neural network-based program to compute the acute toxicity of organic chemicals to the FHM using a proprietary neural network algorithm

12. OASIS	http://www.oasis-lmc.org/ Commercial software software.php	OASIS uses the response-surface approach for modelling acute toxicity for two types of toxico-chemical domains : noncovalent (reversible) acting chemicals and irreversible covalent bioreactive chemicals. Interspecies correlations for acute toxicity to 17 aquatic species, such as fish, snail, tadpole, hydrozoan, crustacean, insect larvae and bacteria have been developed. The Tissue MEtabolism Simulator (TIMES) platform is used to predict the individual and interspecies models for acute aquatic toxicity	
13. DfW	Knowledge-based expert system created with knowledge of structure-toxicity relationships and an emphasis on the need to understand mechanisms of action and metabolism	(a) There are 361 alerts covering a wide range of toxicological end-points (b) An alert consists of a toxicophore (c) The skin sensitization knowledge base in DfW was initially developed in collaboration with Unilever in 1993 using its historical database of GPMT data for 294 chemicals (d) Version 9.0.0 contains 64 alerts for skin sensitization	
14. TIMES-SS Times MEtabolism Simulator platform	Marketed by LMC University "As Zlatarov", Bourgas, Bulgaria	Hybrid Expert Systems	(a) Encode structure toxicity and structure metabolism relationships through a number of transformations simulating skin metabolism and interaction of the generated reactive metabolites with skin proteins (b) The skin metabolism simulator mimics metabolism using 2D structural information (c) The covalent reactions with proteins are described by 47 alerting groups
15. SARET Structure-Activity Relationships for Environmental Toxicology	http://www.ibmh.msk.ru Introduced by Prof. Sergey Novikov, MRC "MEDTOXECO", Department of General Hygiene, Moscow, Russia and by Prof. Vladimir Poroikov, IBMC RAMS,	(a) It consists of SARETbase, SARET model, Computer programs for calculation of descriptors (b) SARETbase includes the information on more than 190 characteristics for 8500 substances : chemical structure, physico-chemical properties (density, boiling and melting points, partition coefficients of	SARETmodel is designed for statistical analysis of data and calculation of unknown parameters of substances on the basis of (Q)SARs. The application of SARET provides the information necessary to evaluate the hazard of chemicals and to estimate their unknown

	Moscow, Russia	octanol/water, etc.), adverse effect doses and concentrations for acute and chronic exposure, odor thresholds in water and air, character of odor, some of threshold limit values for occupational and environmental exposure (air, water)	characteristics. Mathematical models for prediction of toxicological properties of chemicals have been developed	
16	TERA Tools for environmental risk assessment	TERAbase is a part of expert system created by Prof. S. M. Novikov and coauthors from the A. N. Sysin Research Institute of Human Ecology and Environmental Health of Russian Academy of Medical Sciences	(a) TERA includes the information on approximately 200 characteristics for more than 13000 chemical substances. (b) The information collected in SARET and TERA is verified and specified on the basis of both Russian and foreign literature data including official documents, open publications, and "grey" literature (c) TERA contains information for 194 mixtures, 182 polymers, 346 dyes, 1080 non-organic compounds, 1407 remedies, 1260 agrochemicals (including pesticides). More than 1000 compounds contained in TERA are not presented in the Registry of Toxic Effects of Chemical-Substances (RTECS)	TERA contains information useful for human, environmental and ecological risk assessment and management (a) Assessment of multi-domain risk (b) Assessment of carcinogenic potency risk (c) Prediction of lead concentrations in blood of fetus, children, adults (system LRISK) (d) Health risk connected with lead exposure (e) Prediction of emission of chemical substances and their distribution in different media (f) Parameters used for setting priority of chemical substances in risk assessment (g) Risk assessment using epidemiological data
17.	CAESAR	http://www.caesar-project.eu/	CAESAR is an EC funded project (Project no. 022674-SSPI), which is specifically dedicated to develop QSAR models for the REACH legislation	Endpoints addressed : Bioconcentration factor, Skin sensitization, mutagenicity, carcinogenicity, developmental toxicity

molecular-weight molecules such as polymers are limited.

(iii) The other warning is poly-pharmacology. If drugs are acting through multiple mechanisms and hitting multiple safety liability targets, then interpretation of mechanism of action of a compound is difficult in QSAR (*in silico*) study.

(iv) There are important limitations of QSAR models for rodent carcinogenicity. If a test chemical is predicted *in silico* to be of high concern or contain biophores portending to carcinogenic activity in rodents, what does that mean on a mechanistic level? More importantly what is its relevance to human cancer risk assessment of pharmaceuticals? Some rodent tumours are irrelevant to hu-

man cancer risk assessment of drugs^{221,222}

(v) The quality and reproducibility of data used to model toxicity is under question.

(vi) A model's applicability domain is recognized as a major criteria and limitation in the use of *in silico* QSARs in toxicology and pharmacology²²³. Advanced methods for computing applicability domain have been described accounting for mechanistic considerations and metabolism, and for global models a shelf life of an applicability domain of just > 1 year has been suggested²²³. If an *in silico* screened pharmaceutical is not within the applicability domain, the prediction is invalid.

(vii) QSAR employs the strategy of representing molecular structure and correlating it with toxic effects. The

issue of the inability of computational software programs to calculate salt mixtures with small counter ions such as Cl^- or SO_4^{2-} or in hydrated states indicates that a complete representation of the molecule as it is expected to endogenously occur may lead to error in predictive performance because the *in silico* analysis is based on a “disconnected structure”²²⁴.

(viii) Another important factor of human judgment leading to error and bias in consensus-based opinions or expert judging that can be prone to subjectivity leading to inaccuracies²²⁵.

12. Overview and conclusion

It is estimated that 3.9 million laboratory animals might potentially be utilized for testing under the REACH requirements²²⁶. The economic costs of implementing REACH are also very high : over the next 11 years it might cost nearly 2.5 billion euros to test the approximately 30000 substances of which more than 1 ton per year is produced²²⁷. Therefore, *in silico* techniques could be a valuable complement to *in vivo* and *in vitro* studies in assessing hazards of chemicals. On the other hand, most of the new drug entities are discarded during the last phase of drug discovery. Therefore, pre-screening of drug candidates with *in silico* tools can be an option to avoid the loss at later stage. Of course *in silico* approaches cannot replace “wet” experiments but they can be integrated with them. They can set priorities for compounds needing deeper *in vitro* and *in vivo* investigations, for a more rational use of resources by planning experimental testing better. In this regard, we have reviewed here some of the recent reports of chemical and pharmaceutical related toxicities to human and environment and different largely used endpoints for toxicity prediction. QSAR approaches in toxicity predictions are also discussed. Available databases and expert systems for *in silico* approaches have been mentioned. The role of Government organization of different countries for toxicity predictions has also been reported.

This review tries to increase the awareness of *in silico* approaches in chemical toxicity prediction and pre-screening of pharmaceutical toxicity before preclinical trials. As of date, many regulatory authorities and companies are still not taking the advantage of *in silico* approaches,

especially at the developing countries. This report encourages *in silico* approaches to save time, money, animal testing and initial screening of toxicity of chemicals and pharmaceuticals to avoid larger loss at a later part of toxicity investigations.

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